

GEOCOPR Report:

Antarctic Geospace Research Towards IPY5

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GEOCOPR

GEOSPACE EXPLORATION AND OBSERVATION
WITH SCIENTIFIC COLLABORATION IN POLAR REGIONS

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Executive Summary

“What happens at the poles affects us all.” This simple message delivered during the fourth International Polar Year (2007-2008) highlights the importance of polar science to all humanity (National Research Council 2012a). It has proven true time and again for research on interactions between the Sun and near-Earth space, or geospace, as this research has led us to the understanding that polar regions are fundamental to both “discover the secrets of the local cosmos,” including the origins of life, and “to expand and safeguard humanity’s home in space” (NASEM 2024) from space weather impacts that affect human life and technology at all latitudes.

A workshop funded by NSF was held on October 18-20, 2023 by the polar geospace research community to assess progress accomplished since a workshop roughly 10 years earlier, “Solar-Terrestrial Research in Polar Regions: Past, Present, and Future,” (Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax 2014), with a particular emphasis on Antarctica. This report is intended to summarize the discussion from the Geospace Exploration and Observation with Scientific Collaboration in Polar Regions (GEOSCOPR) workshop and place it in context with other reports for several purposes: (1) tracking progress in Antarctic geospace research, (2) identifying key unresolved science questions and gaps in understanding, (3) identifying future measurement and modeling needs to advance the national space weather enterprise, (4) identifying opportunities for international and interdisciplinary partnerships, and (5) discussing the current and future outlook for the state of the profession, education, and outreach. Although this report is not a consensus study, it’s guided by several consensus studies and other reports requested by NSF, NASA, and other agencies; these include the recent solar and space physics (heliophysics) decadal survey (NASEM 2024) and reports from the Space Weather Advisory Group (SWAG, an advisory body created in accordance with PROSWIFT and the Federal Advisory Committee Act).

1 Background and Motivation

“The key to many secrets of Nature...is certainly to be sought for near the Poles. But as long as Polar Expeditions are looked on merely as a sort of international steeple-chase, which is primarily to confer honour upon this flag or other...these mysteries will remain unsolved...”

Lieutenant Karl Weyprecht in address to Royal Geographical Society, 1875

1.1 Importance of Polar Geospace Research and Monitoring

The connections between the space environment over the poles and our everyday lives are everywhere: brilliant aurora over Antarctica lead to changes in the atmosphere and electrical currents that drag communications satellites out of orbit and disrupt power grids; radiation from solar flares detected at the poles provide early warning of radio wave blackouts; airlines divert their flights in response to predicted changes in high altitude radiation; sudden stratospheric warming events disrupt the polar vortex leading to terrestrial weather impacts; and more. At the same time, dynamics in the space environment at the Earth's poles provide a lens into “the only known habitable system in the universe” and opportunities to “understand conditions for life elsewhere in the universe.” The environment at the Earth's poles allows us to sample crucial processes affecting the development life, such as atmospheric escape and the ability of planetary environments with asymmetric magnetic fields to deflect solar radiation.

Studies of the polar regions are essential for geospace researchers. In particular, radiation present in vast regions of geospace is funneled and concentrated by the Earth's magnetic field as it enters both polar regions. This radiation and the

Figure 1.1: All images and captions obtained from the National Weather Service forecast office in Des Moines, Iowa (https://www.weather.gov/dmx/May2024_NorthernLights). Left: Polar orbiting satellite composite of the aurora, which is the brighter white, on the evening of May 10 into the morning of May 11, 2024 as viewed looking down at the North Pole (center) over the northern hemisphere (Source: NESDIS and CIRA). Right: Aurora borealis (bright white in the image) over the continental United States early on the morning of May 11, 2024 as viewed by polar orbiting satellites. (Source: NESDIS and CIRA).

resulting dynamics affect a vast range of processes across geospace, ultimately leading to effects in the atmosphere, the solid Earth, and human life and technology at all latitudes. These connections were brought home to many people across the United States during major recent geomagnetic storms in 2023 and 2024, as dazzling aurora moved equatorward from the poles, becoming visible across the continental US (Figure 1.1) and causing several space weather impacts (Chapter 4).

Measurements at both poles are required to understand and model complex and often asymmetric geospace dynamics. For example, vast regions of geospace are difficult to monitor with sparse, rapidly moving satellite measurements, yet because of the funneling effect of Earth's magnetic field these regions map to relatively small polar regions that can feasibly be instrumented with ground-based networks. The northern hemisphere is significantly better instrumented than the southern hemisphere, and this difference has increased in recent years due to challenges in deploying and maintaining instruments in Antarctica. We know from predictions of increasingly advanced geospace environment models that addressing this difference in measurement coverage would significantly improve our understanding of global geospace dynamics, improve and constrain geospace models, and lead to better nowcasts and forecasts of the space environment. For example, processes such as the aurora in the northern hemisphere are directly linked to southern hemisphere counterparts by electrical currents flowing along the Earth's magnetic field, and space weather impacts related to the aurora (e.g., aurora causing power grid disruptions in the northeastern USA and eastern Canada are closely related to space environment dynamics over the Antarctic peninsula and West Antarctica, Figure 1.2) are likewise linked: what happens at both poles affects us all. Antarctica is a unique platform for geospace observations, and improving measurement capabilities there would improve our understanding of the unique dynamics occurring over the southern hemisphere and fundamental processes relevant to other planetary systems.

In this report, we bring together material from recent geospace research community discussions, reports, and consensus studies to describe the past, present, and desired future state of polar geospace research, with a particular focus on Antarctica.

1.2 Antarctic Geospace Research: Past, Present, and Future

The importance of polar research has been emphasized by past International Polar Years (IPY) which have focused international collaborative research activities to

Figure 1.2: A magnetic projection of the Antarctic coastline to the northern hemisphere for each International Polar Year to date, calculated using AACGMv2. (2024 is used to indicate future investigations, as field projections for 2032 are not yet available at the time of writing.) Over the last 100 years, the projection of the coastline moves as Earth's internally generated magnetic field changes (Collins 2025; Collins et al. 2025). At the time of writing, the space environment over the Antarctic peninsula is magnetically connected to the northeastern USA and eastern Canada, presenting opportunities for coordinated citizen science experiments during IPY5.

advance discovery and understanding of the most pressing geophysical scientific challenges. The first International Polar Year in 1882-1883 ushered in an era of international and interdisciplinary scientific cooperation in polar research, the legacy of which has lasted well beyond 1883. A third International Polar Year (IPY3), better known as the International Geophysical Year (IGY), led to profound changes in our understanding of a range of natural phenomena, from variations in geospace plasmas to plate tectonics. It also cemented the spirit of international collaboration in Antarctica from data sharing via World Data Centers to the subsequent signing of the Antarctic Treaty that preserved the continent for peaceful, scientific purposes. In the USA, IPY3 was remarkable for another reason: the dramatic investment in Antarctic infrastructure including the establishment of permanent bases at McMurdo Sound and South Pole and the required complex supply chains for these bases. Polar regions are no less important for geospace research today, with the growing awareness of natural hazards associated with space weather, the connections between space weather and other disciplines (e.g., upper-lower atmosphere interactions), and the uniqueness of polar regions as natural laboratories for geospace research.

Antarctic measurements, combined with rapidly advancing numerical models, have enabled a steady stream of advances in polar geospace research since IPY3. This report will focus on the last 10-15 years, covering the period since Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), with highlights including better quantification of the profound role north-south hemisphere asymmetries in electrical currents/aurora play in atmospheric heating and global geospace dynamics, how multi-scale ionospheric structures disrupt radio signals, how connections between the lower and upper atmosphere cause sudden stratospheric warming and affect the polar vortex, and more. These examples all have a direct societal benefit through informing our understanding of space weather hazards and connections with terrestrial weather. Many of these advances have also been enabled through both interdisciplinary and international collaboration.

The investments made by the USA in Antarctic infrastructure during IPY3 and IPY4, together with international partners, enabled a discoveries across a wide range of scientific disciplines (National Research Council 2012a). These investments weren't meant to simply establish a US presence in Antarctica to fulfill the "steeple-chase" criticized by Lieutenant Karl Wayprecht in the quote above; instead their purpose was to drive forward discovery using Antarctic measurements as a key to unlock the "many secrets of Nature." For example, polar observations from the Polar Observing Network (POLENET), developed during IPY4 involved researchers from 24 nations and multiple disciplines, represented a dramatic im-

provement in geophysical observations in both the Antarctic and Arctic. It led to a range of discoveries across cryosphere, seismology, and many other disciplines. Serendipitously, POLENET also dramatically improved the coverage of geospace measurements in regions such as West Antarctica due to the multi-use nature of some instruments at POLENET observing sites. POLENET is an excellent foreshadowing of the international and interdisciplinary research and monitoring opportunities that would be possible in the next IPY. At the time of this report, planning for the fifth IPY (IPY5) to be held during 2032-2033 is already underway, with tremendous opportunities for scientific discoveries now and during IPY5 to both “discover the secrets of the local cosmos” and “to expand and safeguard humanity’s home in space” (NASEM 2024).

There are also significant, long-term challenges in maintaining or expanding current U.S. Antarctic geospace measurement capabilities as described in other reports (e.g., USAP 2012; NASEM 2021). This includes impacts on the future polar geospace research and space weather monitoring workforce, as discussed in Chapter 7.

While the challenges are large and complex, they are not insurmountable. In this report, we show that several recent discoveries and pivotal developments, including the passage by Congress of the Promoting Research and Observation of Space Weather to Improve the Forecasting of Tomorrow (PROSWIFT) Act in October 2020 and the publication of the Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics (Heliophysics) in 2024 (NASEM 2024), make the case that Antarctic geospace measurements are more important than ever to fundamental geospace research, interdisciplinary research from Sun to atmosphere to cryosphere/solid Earth, and for safeguarding our home in space and protecting infrastructure critical to the U.S. economy. IPY5 serves as a focal point less than 10 years away to motivate progress in addressing these challenges, including through solutions that are already being implemented by NSF and the U.S. geospace research community in coordination with international and interdisciplinary partners.

1.3 Planning the Future State of Polar Geospace Research

A workshop funded by NSF was held on October 18-20, 2023 by the geospace research community to assess progress accomplished since a workshop roughly 10 years earlier, “Solar-Terrestrial Research in Polar Regions: Past, Present, and Future,” and related report (Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax 2014). The purpose of the 2023 Geospace Exploration and Observation with Scientific Collaboration

in Polar Regions (GEOSOPR) workshop was also to assess the vitality of our polar geospace scientific community, identify important scientific priorities, and begin to organize and plan for the upcoming IPY5 with a particular emphasis on the Antarctic polar research program. Recognizing the increasing challenges in undertaking Antarctic research supported by the U. S. Antarctic Program (USAP), a major focus of the workshop was to engage a range of other scientific communities and international researchers in order to find common areas of interest that could lead to efficiencies and mutual benefit through increased partnerships. Representatives from USAP and NSF were also invited to discuss the current state and future plans for Antarctic infrastructure and NSF geospace research programs. 63 scientists, including many students, participated in the workshop, including representatives from 11 countries. The workshop took place over 3 days with 46 presentations and 7 open discussion sessions, with sessions focused on both the current state of polar geospace research, desired future state, and discussion of how to get there by IPY5.

This report is intended to summarize the discussion from the GEOSOPR workshop and place it in context with Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) and other reports/consensus studies for several purposes: (1) tracking progress in Antarctic geospace research, (2) identifying key unresolved science questions and gaps in understanding, (3) identifying future measurement and modeling needs to advance the national space weather enterprise, (4) identifying opportunities for international and interdisciplinary partnerships, and (5) discussing the current and future outlook for the state of the profession, education, and outreach. Although this report is not a consensus study with specific findings and recommendations, it's guided by several consensus studies and other reports requested by NSF, NASA, and other agencies; these include the recent solar and space physics (heliophysics) decadal survey (NASEM 2024), reports from the Space Weather Advisory Group (SWAG, an advisory body created in accordance with PROSWIFT and the Federal Advisory Committee Act), and reports such as "A Strategic Vision for NSF Investments in Antarctic and Southern Ocean Research" (NASEM 2015). Throughout this report, we connect discussions from the GEOSOPR workshop with specific findings and recommendations from these other studies and reports.

The report is organized around several themes discussed at the workshop and in follow-on discussions at other meetings. Chapter 2 and 3 focus primarily on high-priority science questions including interdisciplinary research. Chapter 4 focuses on the applied side of Antarctic research for space weather monitoring and operational data products. Chapter 5 primarily focuses on facilities/infrastructure at bases and the deep field as well as observing strategies for achieving the goals in

the previous Chapters. Chapter 6 focuses on international, interdisciplinary, and other partnerships. Finally, Chapter 7 focuses on the state of the profession.

It's hoped that this report will serve as a resource to demonstrate how Antarctic geospace research and monitoring are crucial to the solar and space physics community's vision to "discover the secrets of the local cosmos" and "to expand and safeguard humanity's home in space" (NASEM 2024).

2 Solar Wind-Magnetosphere-Ionosphere Interactions

“The difficulty was that one pole has daylight when it is night at the other pole. You probably could not see an aurora in bright sunlight, increased by the glare from the snow on the ground, even if one took place. Moreover, you never had observers both in the far north and in the far south at the same moment. But, during the IGY, you do have observers all over. And they were aided by new instrumentation which would have sounded like magic in the days of Nansen [. . .] There is no way of prophesying how many scientific papers and books in the future will begin with the words: ‘It was first noticed during the IGY that...’ but it’s certain that the number will not be small.”

Willy Ley, *Galaxy Science Fiction*, 1958

Relevant Documents with Recommendations and Findings

In addition to the workshop proceedings, this section draws on recommendations and findings from several consensus studies and other reports including especially “The Next Decade of Discovery in Solar and Space Physics: Exploring and Safeguarding Humanity’s Home in Space” (NASEM 2024) and “Solar-Terrestrial Research in Polar Regions: Past, Present, and Future” (Lessard, Gerard, and Weatherwax 2014). Although this report is not a consensus study, where appropriate we identify connections between items discussed at the workshop to specific science questions, goals, and recommendations from other relevant reports and consensus studies.

Measurements in the sparsely sampled Antarctic and Southern Ocean, coupled with rapidly advancing models, are crucial for understanding and monitoring solar wind-magnetosphere-ionosphere interactions; it's not possible to understand or monitor these interactions with Arctic measurements alone. For example, we know that these asymmetries play important roles in driving space weather and related impacts on a range of scales (e.g., enhanced atmospheric drag on LEO satellites), yet many space weather predictions from increasingly advanced models cannot currently be tested due to a lack of southern hemisphere measurements. Thus, Antarctic measurements, coupled with advanced models are crucial to the geospace research community's mission "to serve humanity" by analysis of "the space environment to project its future changes" and by the "development of tools and products to issue space weather warnings and forecasts." (NASEM 2024). Indeed, NASEM (2024) specifically calls out the need for "simultaneous observations of auroral and ionospheric processes at both hemispheres" as well as models "with capability to resolve smaller mesoscale processes that have large-scale impacts" (Table 2-1 in NASEM 2024). The authors also note (page 57), "it has been shown that auroral processes in the two hemispheres contain unexplained asymmetries...While it would be important to include such asymmetries in physics-based models, the lack of observations from the southern hemisphere limits the ability to quantify the asymmetries. Major advances in this area could be made by imaging the auroral distributions simultaneously over both hemispheres. Important synergy is achieved by combining these observations with observations of the ground magnetic field disturbances and field-aligned current patterns..."

North-south hemisphere asymmetries are also common in planetary magnetospheres/ionospheres throughout our solar system and beyond, thus an improved understanding of the role of north-south hemisphere asymmetries in energy transfer, mass and energy outflow, and electrodynamic coupling is essential to understand the fundamental physics of planetary magnetospheres. Thus, Antarctic measurements are also relevant to the space physics community's mission to "develop models and theories that explain the physics and interconnections of the heliosphere and to understand conditions for life elsewhere in the universe" and to use geospace "to gain a view of the only known habitable system in the universe" (NASEM 2024).

Interhemispheric Asymmetries

The energy that enters the Earth's magnetosphere and gets translated to the atmosphere does not always manifest equally in both hemispheres. Solar wind-magnetosphere coupling plays a role in this variation, as does differences in pre-conditioning due to seasonal changes and localized magnetic field asymmetries. The Earth's weaker southern polar magnetic field also has a number of consequences for SWMI coupling, including increased energetic particle precipitation into the southern ionosphere that affects ionospheric conductivity and a range of electrodynamic coupling processes. While much of the Arctic throughout Alaska, Canada, Greenland and Fenno-Scandia is heavily instrumented, we don't have comparable networks in the Antarctic by which to observe the asymmetric geospace processes. A global understanding of energy input, redistribution, and the effects those have on human enterprise necessitates a holistic, interhemispheric view of the system.

The presence of north-south hemisphere asymmetries highlight the importance of the high-latitude southern hemisphere to our understanding of the geospace environment and space weather. In this Chapter, we provide a brief introduction to SWMI coupling followed by several sections related to more specific science topics and questions that can only be fully addressed, or are best addressed, with southern hemisphere measurements and models that account for the unique dynamics of both hemispheres. In the final section, we provide a past, present, and future outlook to SWMI coupling research based on questions and observing strategies described roughly 10 years ago in Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), the present state of SWMI coupling research based on discussions at the GEOSCOPR workshop and text in the decadal survey NASEM (2024), and a future goals. For a more detailed discussion of atmosphere-ionosphere interactions see Chapter 3, for a more detailed discussion of how Antarctic measurements and related models can improve space weather forecasts and nowcasts see Chapter 4, and for observing strategies for achieving future goals see Chapters 5 and 6.

2.1 Solar Wind-Magnetosphere-Ionosphere Interactions: Introduction

At high latitudes under most conditions, geospace phenomena are driven primarily by the solar wind and interplanetary magnetic field (IMF). Driving comes through

the coupling of mass, momentum, and energy at magnetopause at the subsolar point (during periods of southward IMF) or on the magnetotail lobes (during periods of northward IMF). In the coupling, solar wind plasma enters the magnetosphere to provide much of its plasma population; solar wind kinetic energy and momentum drive circulation of plasma and magnetic flux within the magnetosphere, which leads to large-scale reconfiguration of the magnetosphere. The circulation and resulting pressure distribution drive electrical currents and energetic precipitation into the upper atmosphere and can result in geomagnetic storms and substorms. Currents and energetic particles coming into the upper atmosphere heat the ionosphere and atmosphere, and create ionospheric plasma. The currents also drive electric fields in the ionosphere, which can lead to structuring of the ionospheric plasma. These currents are also responsible for ground magnetic perturbations, which in return can induce currents in power-transmission lines, oil and gas pipelines, and other infrastructure. Each of these phenomena has the potential to influence our daily lives through impacts on the technology on which we rely. For example, ionospheric conditions developing over the Antarctic directly influence upper atmosphere dynamics that can lead to loss of tracking of satellites or unplanned re-entry as well as electrical currents in the northern hemisphere that affect power grids in the USA, Canada, etc. (see Chapter 4).

Observing the signatures and consequences of the coupling enables us to understand the physical processes responsible for the coupling, and the physical processes acting within the magnetosphere, ionosphere, and upper atmosphere that redistribute the mass, momentum, and energy throughout geospace and result in technological impacts. The coupling occurs far out in the magnetosphere, however it is possible to discern much about the phenomena using ground-based observations in the locations where the magnetic field lines connect to the regions of interest in the magnetosphere or at the magnetopause. This is possible because the near infinite conductivity along magnetic field lines results in signatures of the processes appearing in the ionosphere and upper atmosphere where remote sensing instruments can observe them.

Due to the dipole geometry of the Earth's magnetic field, the polar regions intersect the field lines that reach significant distances into the magnetosphere. For example, the latitude of a dipolar magnetic field line that reaches geosynchronous orbits (~ 6.6 Earth Radii) intersects the ionosphere at close to 65 degrees latitude. Observations of the signature of magnetic field lines mapping to the dayside magnetopause show that they typically occur above 70 degrees magnetic latitude (e.g., P. T. Newell, Wing, and Rich 2007). Because of this mapping, observations from polar regions are required for understanding solar wind-magnetosphere-ionosphere-

atmosphere coupling. Observations from Antarctica are particularly useful because the landmass of the continent enables deployment of instruments at the critical latitudes that are inaccessible from northern lands.

This fact, as well as other advantages of Antarctica as an observing platform, was noted by Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), "In general, Antarctica samples a vast region of the AIM environment and indeed provides a unique window for a number of important scientific reasons. Unlike the northern hemisphere, ground-based observations of processes at very high latitudes, albeit logistically difficult, are possible in Antarctica. By contrast, these latitudes in the northern hemisphere lie mainly in the Arctic ocean. Consequently, a distributed ground-based array in the Antarctic is the only possible way to provide near-global coverage at high geomagnetic latitudes." This point is illustrated in Figure 2.1 showing lines of constant magnetic latitude at 65 and 80 degrees in both hemispheres; significantly more land area is available in southern hemisphere regions mapping to the polar cap and cusp regions.

Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) also notes, "Antarctica also has an advantage over the northern polar regions in terms of optical observation of day-side auroral phenomena. This is due to the fact that the southern magnetic pole has a larger offset from the geographic pole than occurs in the north by nearly 10 degrees. Therefore, the high geographic latitudes in the south are well suited for dayside auroral studies in terms of the magnetic mapping to the aurora oval and also the extended periods of darkness at midday (e.g. South Pole has 3 months of total darkness during winter)." Figure 2.2 illustrates these points by showing solar illumination as a function of time of day (y-axis) and month (x-axis) for stations in the northern hemisphere (top row) and their approximate magnetic conjugate station in the southern hemisphere (bottom row). Syowa Station in Antarctica is in darkness the entire day during southern winter (July, center of bottom right plot) making it possible to observe the entire range of auroral phenomena, while its counterpart in the northern hemisphere at Husafell experiences periods of daylight year round, including winter (top right plot), and thus cannot observe the entire range of auroral phenomena.

In the next few sections, we discuss a few high-priority geospace research areas where Antarctic measurements are particularly crucial due to (1) the need to observe both hemispheres simultaneously to account for hemispheric asymmetries, (2) the unique advantages of Antarctica as an observing platform, or both.

Figure 2.1: Graticules at $\pm 65^\circ$ and $\pm 80^\circ$ magnetic latitude are superimposed on the polar regions, denoting the general area of the auroral oval. While most of the relevant area in the Arctic is covered by the Arctic Ocean and therefore unsuitable for instrument deployments, the overlap of the southern magnetic pole with the Antarctic continent enables high-latitude measurements on land. Magnetic latitudes were obtained using Altitude Adjusted Corrected Geomagnetic Coordinates version 2.0 with the 2020 version of the International Geomagnetic Reference Field. (Collins et al. 2025)

Figure 2.2: Sun graphs are presented showing day and night patterns at northern hemisphere stations (Resolute Bay and Husafell) and their approximate Antarctic counterparts (McMurdo Station and Syowa Station). The horizontal axis for each plot represents one year; the vertical axis, hours in UTC from bottom to top. Dark and light portions of each plot indicate night and day; on the right side, blue and yellow lines indicate local midnight and noon, respectively. Since auroral observations must be conducted in darkness, stations in both hemispheres are required to monitor aurorae throughout the day. Plot by Kristina Collins, code by Price-Whelan (2022)

2.2 Direct Influence of the Solar Wind and IMF in the Polar Cap

The dynamics of the plasma and magnetic field in polar regions are influenced by direct coupling from the solar wind and the IMF. The coupling comes because during periods of southward IMF, merging between terrestrial field lines with the IMF at the dayside magnetopause creates a region where the terrestrial field lines can be mapped from the ionosphere through the magnetopause and out to the solar wind. These polar cap field lines connect directly to the IMF and allow particles and MHD waves from the solar wind to penetrate to ionospheric altitudes. The linkage between magnetic field fluctuations (e.g., Ultra Low Frequency [ULF] waves) observed in the polar cap and those in the solar wind has been shown in previous studies. It has also been shown that there is a close correspondence between ULF waves in the Pc5 range (2-10 Hz) in the inner magnetosphere and solar wind velocity (M. Engebretson et al. 1998) or solar wind dynamic pressure (Kepko and Spence 2003), though closely spaced measurements from Antarctic magnetometer networks have revealed significant north-south hemisphere asymmetries in Pc5 wave properties (Kim et al. 2017; Shi et al. 2020). Yagova et al. (2002) also suggested that ULF waves in the polar cap may be related to direct penetration of solar wind; 2) variations of open-closed boundary (OCB) as shown using the occurrences of Pc5 wave activity observed by the Antarctic magnetometer network (e.g., K. D. Urban et al. 2011; K. Urban et al. 2016; Frissell et al. 2024).

The physical link between solar wind variations and ULF wave occurrence and their spectral characteristics has not been extensively studied. Besides their possible close correspondence, waves, generated from the inner magnetosphere, can propagate within the ionosphere horizontally, being observed deep in the polar cap. Therefore, investigation of wave sources can provide important information about how the solar wind plays a role in the physical process of ULF wave generation and propagation in the polar cap. Wave occurrence and propagation are closely associated with not only the magnetospheric dynamics but also the ionospheric conditions such as conductivity.

Furthermore, during prolonged southward IMF BZ and low-intensity solar wind driving, the particles from the Sun's corona can directly enter the Earth's upper atmosphere in the Arctic and Antarctic regions, the hemispheric preference thought to be determined by the IMF BX conditions (Zhang, Paxton, and Lui 2007). Referred to as polar rain, the energy of the precipitating particles originating from corona can range from eV to keV range, controlling the ionospheric conductance and consequently the physical processes across polar cap (Patrick T. Newell and Meng 1990). The electrodynamics as a result of polar rain could significantly dif-

fer between the two hemispheres altering the global dynamics. However, its full characterization is severely lacking both statistically and in numerical models due to the phenomenon and its detection from ground being very rare (Hosakawa et al. 2024).

Antarctica provides a platform for ground-based instruments to observe the plasma dynamics and magnetic field perturbations, which can provide insights into the various coupling processes. The dynamics may include 1) magnetic field fluctuations (e.g., ULF waves); 2) variations in the latitude of the open-closed boundary (OCB); 3) ionospheric irregularities affecting radio wave propagation and Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) TEC and scintillation measurements (see Chapter 3; 4) particulate precipitation and auroral occurrences (“transpolar arc” or “theta aurora”) in association with substorms.

2.3 Observation of Flux Transport Across Central Polar Cap and Relation to the Substorm Cycle

Antarctic SuperDARN observes cusp latitudes and polar cap latitudes very well. It is the one way in which the southern hemisphere network excels over the northern hemisphere network. With this excellent geometry, the radars are well positioned to observe dayside plasma entry. High-resolution vector plasma flow maps illustrate that the flows are often bursty and form isolated regions that move poleward into the dayside throat and remain coherent as they propagate across the polar cap. In the coming years we will quantify this and investigate the link to night-side poleward boundary intensifications and their connection to substorm onsets.

As an example of bursty flow observations in the cusp region, Figure 2.3 (a) shows the flow observed in the Antarctic polar cap at 1755 UT on 23 February, 2022, and (b) a time series of the flows along the 1100 MLT meridian for a two-hour interval centered on 1800 UT. The map view shows a region of flow in the dayside throat region (the region where plasma enters the polar cap) that has higher velocity than the surrounding observations. The region is centered at about 1100 MLT between the 75° and 80° magnetic latitude. In the time series view, the flow vectors at those latitudes are seen to increase from about 600 m/s at 1745 UT to about 1000 m/s at the time of the map. The burst of flow shows clear evidence of poleward propagation after its initial observation. A similar shorter lived burst with similar propagation is evident at about 1730 UT.

Figure 2.3: (a) Map of plasma flows observed over the Antarctic continent at 1755 UT on 23 February 2022. The two solid black lines show the 1100 MLT and the 1300 MLT meridians. Colored vectors show where radar observations were located. (b) A time series of flows along the 1100 MLT meridian over the interval from 1700 UT to 1900 UT.

2.4 Auroral and Plasma Physics

Antarctica has always been a critical platform for passive observations of auroral radio emissions, because radio frequency interference from human activity and communications at non-Antarctic locations obscures many of these emissions. These observations serve several important purposes. First, the auroral plasma physics processes that generate them are of intrinsic interest not only to auroral physics but also to the physics of planetary, solar, and astrophysical environments in which similar physics results in similar emissions. Second, observable characteristics of these emissions provide means of remotely sensing plasma conditions and processes in their source regions and in the ionosphere through which they propagate. Third, in some cases radio emissions through wave-particle interactions directly affect or control plasma boundaries or particle populations in space physics. These factors motivate maintaining and enhancing passive observations of auroral radio emissions at Very Low Frequencies (VLF) and High Frequencies (HF) in the Antarctic.

2.5 Impacts of Meso-scale Structure and Asymmetries on Global Dynamics

At high latitudes magnetospheric driving of the ionosphere is a major heat source for the neutral atmosphere. The heat comes from collisions between ions and the neutral constituents, which is a function of the neutral density, the ion density, and the ion velocity. The ion velocity is driven by the electric fields imposed by the magnetosphere, while the ion density is controlled by solar extreme ultraviolet (EUV) irradiance, energetic particle precipitation, and evolution under the influence of chemical processes and advection. Heating of the upper atmosphere alters its density profile, causing increases in the density at altitudes above the region of heating. The expansion comes because the atmosphere is nearly in hydrostatic equilibrium; i.e. the vertical pressure gradient force balances the gravitational force. Localized heating increases the temperature, which alters the pressure gradient leading to an adjustment of the density profile in order to reestablish the force balance. Variations of the neutral atmospheric density at high altitudes influence the velocity of satellites in low-Earth-orbit. Understanding and predicting the variations is necessary for characterization of those orbits.

North-south and east-west asymmetries in mesoscale dayside (ion foreshock transients, magnetosheath jets, magnetopause surface waves, ULF waves) and nightside (dipolarizing flux bundles, ULF waves) transients ultimately affect hemispheric asymmetries in magnetosphere-ionosphere current systems/waves and associated thermospheric heating rates. Observations (both space- and ground-based) have in many cases lacked the spatial coverage to test these predictions and pinpoint which processes are most important. The same is true for geomagnetic disturbance (GMD) - some of these transients have been linked to fairly extreme GMD, but we usually lack the observations to show which phenomena drive the most extreme GMD and/or the spatial distribution of the GMD. One exception relates to combined magnetometer networks that have enabled the remote sensing of ionospheric current systems through use of the Spherical Elementary Current Systems technique (Weygand et al. 2023). As shown in Figure 2.4 and demonstrated in several recent papers, the combination of closely spaced magnetometers in North America, Greenland, and East Antarctica for the first time enabled the remote sensing of mesoscale ionospheric currents in both hemispheres simultaneously, making it possible to quantify north-south asymmetries related to a variety of processes including large amplitude GMD that can drive geomagnetically induced currents in power grids and other infrastructure (M. J. Engebretson

Figure 2.4: Top Row: Example interhemispheric comparison of ionospheric currents derived from magnetometer networks using the SECS technique from an event examined by Weygand et al. (2023). Bottom Row: The same measurements superimposed derived field-aligned currents using fitting to magnetometer data from Iridium satellites. The dense network of magnetometers enables the detection of structure in mesoscale currents, some of which cannot be remote sensed via AMPERE (e.g., Hall and Pedersen currents, currents varying on timescales $< \sim 10$ minutes)

et al. 2022).

2.6 SWMI Coupling: Past, Present, and Future

NASEM (2024) describes the wider geospace research community's highest priority research goals and observations for the next decade. This includes several overarching science themes and related guiding questions that flow down into the more focused objectives mentioned in this Chapter:

1. Science Theme "Sun-Earth-Space: Our Interconnected Home"
 - (a) The overarching question "How do the Sun-Earth system parts interact with each other?" includes focus areas "Magnetic connections across the heliosystem" and "Multiple drivers and feedback mechanisms," requiring auroral and ionospheric plasma remote sensing measurements and simultaneous observations of auroral and ionospheric processes at both hemispheres (Table 2-1 in NASEM (2024)). The topics described in sections 2.2-2.5 are all related to this overarching question. More broadly, Antarctic geospace observations are essential to address this question as simultaneous measurements in both hemispheres are a requirement.
 - (b) The overarching question "How do heliosystem boundaries manifest themselves?" includes focus areas "System impacts of magnetic boundary processes" and requires multi-plane, multi-altitude measurements of auroral and outflow processes. The topic described in section 2.4 and to a lesser extent other sections are related to this overarching question
2. Science Theme "A Laboratory in Space: Building Blocks of Understanding"
 - (a) The overarching question "How do fundamental processes create and dissipate explosive phenomena across the heliosphere?" includes focus areas such as the "Response of systems to explosive events," and requires ground-based observations of high latitude magnetospheric and solar wind energy deposition (Table 2-2 in NASEM (2024)). The topics described in section 2.2 and 2.3 relate most closely to this question.
 - (b) The overarching question "How do the fundamental processes govern the cross-scale coupling and what are the global properties and consequences of the processes?" includes focus areas such as the "Cross-

scale implications of magnetic reconnection” and requires global measurements of key Ionosphere-Thermosphere-Mesosphere (ITM) parameters. The topics described in all sections are relevant to this overarching question.

To summarize, several of the high priority science goals of the geospace research community as described in NASEM (2024) flow down into the science topics discussed in this sections.

Some aspects of the topics described in this Chapter were also described in Chapter 2 of Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), including specific topics such as mesoscale geomagnetic disturbances known as Traveling Convection Vortices, polar cap patches, different types of aurora, etc. Progress has been made on several of these science questions through, for example, the continued operation of SuperDARN, limited networks of other ground-based instruments, and increasingly advanced models. For example, during a brief period in 2015-2017, there were enough magnetometer networks operating simultaneously that it was possible to perform north-south hemisphere comparisons in both latitude and longitude in a narrow local time sector (Figure 2.4), and this has led to several recent advances in our understanding of the generation mechanisms of GMD and related ionospheric currents that affect space weather.

However, progress in addressing many of the science questions described by Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) (and also the broader questions in NASEM (2024)) has been hindered by the lack of widespread measurements outside of major bases, the uneven sampling of the Antarctic continent with different instrumentation (rather than co-location of measurements), and the lack of continuous monitoring at fixed locations. This has made it difficult to implement the proposed observing strategies in Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), such as the need for magnetometer measurements in West Antarctica and expanded networks over East Antarctica. An example of how this lack of spatial coverage has limited progress can be found in Smith et al. (2023). They simulated ionospheric heating during a geomagnetic storm through an assimilative framework, finding (1) that there were significant north-south hemisphere asymmetries and (2) “Realistic drivers may produce more frequent and intense localized heating events.” At the same time, they noted that they assimilated data from 217 ground magnetometers in their simulation to constrain ionospheric parameters used as model boundary conditions, noting that there were “173 in the northern hemisphere and 44 in the southern hemisphere.” This difference in data coverage, coupled with the increasing recognition of the importance of asymmetric and localized heating

that may be missed in the sparsely sampled southern hemisphere, point to the need for expanded Antarctic measurement networks.

The left part of Figure 2.5 from Alfonsi et al. (2022) highlights a further challenge with southern hemisphere measurements: in many cases, complementary instruments are not co-located. For example, magnetometers provide diagnostics of ionospheric current and are primarily located in East Antarctica, whereas GNSS receivers can be used to constrain ionospheric electron density but are primarily located in West Antarctica. Thus, at most locations it's not possible to measure the full set of ionospheric parameters needed to constrain global space weather models. Moreover, many of the GNSS and magnetometers shown in Figure 2.5 are no longer operating or will be decommissioned soon, highlighting a challenge in long-term monitoring needed to understand drivers that vary on solar cycle timescales, including extreme events such as geomagnetic storms.

To address questions posed in Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) and also in the recent decadal survey (NASEM 2024), many of the same observing strategies proposed by Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) would need to be implemented, including distributed networks with limited instrumentation (e.g., GNSS receivers, magnetometers) in West and East Antarctica anchored by a wider set of instrumentation at major bases. One of the most important lessons learned from the last IPY in 2007-2008 is the transformational impact of large interdisciplinary and international ground-based networks such as POLENET (see Chapter 1 and National Research Council (2012a)) which was not developed by geospace researchers but nevertheless benefited the geospace research community. Moving towards the next IPY in 2032, it's essential to work across disciplines to plan the optimal set of instrumentation for the next IPY. Chapters 5 and 6 will discuss observing strategies to address unresolved science questions further, including the "Distributed Arrays of Small Heterogeneous Instruments" (DASHI) concept, one of the highest-priority ground-based, mid-scale projects recommended by NASEM (2024).

Figure 2.5: Fig 1 from Alfonsi et al. (2022). Scientific instrumentation infrastructure in Antarctica and Arctic regions (selected established stations to indicate the coverage of measurements).

3 Atmosphere-Ionosphere Interactions

“Over the past three decades the scientific community has become more aware of the enormous role that the Earth’s high latitude middle atmosphere plays in the larger global atmospheric circulation and as a modulator of mass/energy entering and leaving the geospace environment. Neutral atmospheric dynamics and atmosphere-ionosphere coupling processes in polar regions represent key dynamics in the global weather, space weather, climate systems, and much of the forcing of the large scale circulation and thermal structure of the global atmosphere stems from polar regions. Furthermore, there are significant differences at polar latitudes between hemispheres in the mean wind and temperature fields and the large-scale atmospheric tides, planetary waves, and gravity waves.”

Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014)

As noted by Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), “this polar middle atmospheric gateway is still poorly understood due to the inherent difficulty in exploring this region; both technically and logistically. Thus, there is a compelling need to better understand the role of middle atmospheric dynamics and chemistry at high latitudes.”

Measurements and models of the polar atmosphere and its interactions with the ionosphere are key for addressing several guiding questions in the solar and space physics decadal survey, including “How do the components of the Sun-Earth system interact with each other?” and “How do the fundamental processes govern the cross-scale coupling and what are the global properties and consequences of these processes?” which requires a focus on understanding the nature and consequences of coupling between ionized and neutral fluids. They can also be used to address “What internal and external characteristics have played a role in

creating a space environment conducive to life?" (NASEM 2024).

In this Chapter, we include several sections related to Atmosphere-Ionosphere (AI) coupling processes. In the final section, we provide a past, present, and future outlook to AI interactions research based on questions and observing strategies described roughly 10 years ago in Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), current state based on discussions at the GEOSOPR workshop and text in the decadal survey (NASEM 2024), and future goals. For a more detailed discussion of solar wind-magnetosphere-ionosphere (SWMI) interactions and general introduction of North-South Hemisphere asymmetries and their consequences see Chapter 2, for a more detailed discussion of how Antarctic measurements and related models can improve space weather forecasts and nowcasts see Chapter 4, and for observing strategies to achieve future goals see Chapters 5 and 6.

3.1 Effects of energetic particle precipitation on the middle atmosphere composition

Energetic particle precipitation can propagate to the low-altitude I-T system altering the composition and density. Some of the most important of these constituents are nitric oxides and hydrogen oxides, because of their role in ozone loss (Sinhuber et al., 2012). These chemical changes are produced at the altitude where precipitating particles ionize, with higher incident energies reaching lower altitudes (Thorne 1980; Baker et al. 1987). Nitric oxides have long lifetimes in the polar night and can therefore linger longer in the polar winter, sometimes being efficiently transported to stratospheric altitudes by the polar vortex (C. Randall et al. 2006). Once they reach the ozone-rich stratosphere, they catalytically destroy ozone resulting in long-lived localized ozone losses (Verronen et al. 2021). Comparisons between observations of atmospheric composition and whole atmosphere model simulations, such as WACCM, have shown mismatches (C. E. Randall et al. 2005), leading to speculation that the energetic particle influence is not accurately captured in the current models.

More recent studies (Bossert et al. 2023) have shown that these energetic particles can also cause CO₂ emission enhancements observed by the AIRS satellite. With the different and changing vertical atmospheric profiles between the Arctic and Antarctic, the characterization and impact of energetic particle precipitation on the Mesosphere and Lower Thermosphere pose various significant open questions. Energetic particle precipitation from the ring current and radiation belts, including high-energy types of aurora like pulsating aurora, are implicated in these

Figure 3.1: Example IH asymmetry from Hong et al. (2023). From paper: Snapshots of the FAC-driven convection patterns (top) for the Southern Hemisphere (SH) driven by different AMIE electron precipitation patterns at 04 UT on October 9 as an example (for 2012-10-08 at 22 UT, somewhat different time than the paper): the SH precipitation itself (A), mirrored precipitation pattern in the geomagnetic field coordinate from the Northern Hemisphere (NH, (B), and their difference (C). The corresponding energy flux of the precipitation patterns for the SH (D), NH(E), and their difference (F) are shown in the bottom.

terrestrial climate impacts (Turunen et al. 2016) and are worth studying further from the polar vantage points.

As discussed in Chapter 2, there are many types of North-South Hemisphere asymmetries that play important roles in Atmosphere-Ionosphere (AI) coupling processes. In the past 10 years, there have been significant advances in numerical simulation capabilities that have made it possible to assess how these asymmetries affect the global coupled system. For example, Figure 3.1 adapted from Hong et al. (2023) shows how different assumptions for symmetric and asymmetric boundary conditions relevant to a particular time period ultimately effect global energy deposition rates from precipitating particles. It also illustrates (1) advances in our ability to assimilate both ground and space-based measurements to constrain global models and (2) the fact that Southern Hemisphere measurements play a crucial role in constraining the global system response (in one case, the boundary condition includes data assimilated from the Southern Hemisphere while in the other it does not). Although modeling capabilities developed considerably since the Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) report, there is still a need to (1) routinely account for the Earth's realistic magnetic field geometry, which is asymmetric and includes higher order (non-dipolar) moments, (2) routinely assimilate measurements from both hemispheres rather than assuming the Southern Hemisphere is a mirror image of the north, and (3) better constrain how driving from the magnetosphere impacts the atmosphere/ionosphere system by including missing physics (e.g., auroral particle acceleration), use of a height-resolved atmosphere/ionosphere in coupled solar wind-magnetosphere-ionosphere-atmosphere models, etc.

3.2 Neutral wind characterization in the polar regions

The characterization of neutral wind and its response to geomagnetic activity at the high latitude regions is crucial as many physical processes that couple the ionosphere and thermosphere, such as momentum transfer, chemical reactions, and the frictional and collisional heating rates rely on accurate determination of the neutral wind vector (Deng and Ridley, 2006). This is not only required for understanding the spatiotemporal scales with which the ionospheric convection can modulate the horizontal neutral wind component (Billett et al., 2019) but also for understanding underexplored or evolving topics such as neutral upwelling (Sojka et al., 2001), flywheel effect (Deng et al., 1993 and references therein) and more recently reported patterns such as wind wall (Shepherd and Shepherd (2018); Barreto-

Schuler et al., (2021)). All these phenomena demonstrate north-south asymmetries, primarily due to density differences caused by solar EUV, and would benefit greatly from multi-point neutral wind vector measurements.

3.3 Polar vortex and sudden stratospheric warming events

Recent studies have shown that the polar vortex, which is the low-pressure, cold, rotating air encircling Earth's poles, could extend from the troposphere to the mesosphere causing top-down and bottom-up coupling between them (Harvey et al., 2022 and references therein). The primary mechanisms that couple these regions are energetic particle precipitation, gravity waves, planetary waves, tidal interactions and consequent changes related to these phenomena, including neutral wind shears, and travelling atmospheric and ionospheric disturbances. Another important mechanism for the bottom-up coupling of the polar ionosphere-thermosphere regions is the sudden stratospheric warming (SSW) events. Goncharenko et al. (2021) reported that SSWs can lead to large-scale ionospheric anomalies in the middle to low-latitude regions as demonstrated by variations in TEC and O/N₂ ratios at times reaching 100% of the baseline values lasting weeks. Furthermore, SSW events can occur concurrently in high-latitude regions, leading to the disruption, displacement, deformation, or cessation of polar vortices (Manney et al., 2022). Reports of SSW events are limited, making observations of their mutual occurrences and interactions with polar vortices even rarer. However, observing and analyzing these events are essential for determining the intricate coupling mechanisms within the dynamic geospace system.

3.4 Polar cap patches, ionospheric irregularities, and scintillation

GNSS signals propagating through ionospheric plasma irregularity structures experience amplitude fading and phase fluctuation, collectively refers to as ionospheric scintillation. Ionospheric scintillation can adversely impact all radio-based systems such as global navigation satellite system (GNSS) and satellite communication. The polar ionosphere is home to many complex processes which create or transport plasma structures to other regions. Therefore, the polar ionosphere offers a unique opportunity to enable passive observations of ionospheric response to the ionospheric and space weather effects. However, there are only sparsely distributed GNSS receivers in Antarctica (see Figure 2.5 in previous Chapter), due to

the challenges in deploying and operating them. Some of the receivers are legacy systems that do not take full advantage of the large number of the latest multiple constellations, multiple frequency bands GNSS (multi-GNSS) signals. Moreover, these GNSS receiver often cease to function properly when the most interesting strong solar and geomagnetic storms occur as these receivers cannot track signals at deep fading levels. Both of these factors prevent the receivers from capturing many dynamic processes, such as instabilities arising from auroral precipitation; for this, more advanced receivers are needed that are capable of capturing, for example, scintillation indices. Ideally, GNSS scintillation receivers that can measure scintillation indices at shorter time scales (i.e., computing variance over 1 s instead of 60 s) would be deployed to help capture fast-moving processes. Better yet, recording the 50 Hz samples will be enable the most flexible post-processing and ability to capture the most dynamic processes. Regardless, more GNSS receivers are needed, and these should ideally be combined with other instruments (e.g., ISR) sensitive to other scales (based on wavelength) to observe energy cascading across multiple scales.

To further exacerbate the problem is a large void over the polar cap where there are no GNSS satellites due to their orbit inclinations. This makes it challenging to analyze measurements which are often collected with very low elevation angles. On flat ice plateaus in Antarctica where you have minimal opportunity for multipath, this is still feasible though adds a layer of complexity. One possible alternative/additional strategy is to use Beacon UHF/VHF receivers with transmitters on LEO satellites.

Another strategy is to use Spaceborne measurements. Spaceborne measurements have already been used to augment the sparse ground-based GNSS receivers' observations in Antarctica. GNSS-RO and GNSS-R are two powerful LEO satellite-based techniques that hold the most promise to fill the ionospheric irregularities data gap. GNSS-RO is a mature technique following the completion of the successful COSMIC mission. In recent years, there are several commercial small satellite companies such as Spire Global and PlanetiQ, who have launched polar-orbiting CubeSats to perform ionospheric measurements over high latitudes. NASA and NOAA have purchased data through the Commercial SmallSat Data Acquisition (CSDA) Program. GNSS-R is an emerging technique that takes advantage of strong reflection signals over ice to infer ionospheric observations over the polar areas. Both GNSS-RO and GNSS-R require ground-based GNSS receivers for calibration and validation. Figure 3.2 illustrates polar ionosphere observations using multiple data sources from GNSS-RO, GNSS-R, ground receivers, and in situ sensors to map and localize ionospheric plasma structures.

Figure 3.2: Illustration of polar ionosphere observation using multiple data sources from GNSS-RO, GNSS-R, ground receivers, and in situ sensors to map and localize ionospheric plasma structures. Credit: Y. Jade Morton

When a GNSS receiver outputs not only scintillation indices but also power and phase samples at 50-100 Hz, researchers can observe variations at smaller time scales for investigating processes during scintillation. Combined with other sensing modalities, such as all-sky imagers, these can be powerful methods for sensing ionospheric dynamics. As an example, Figure 3.3 shows (a) a map of GPS scintillation receivers sited in the auroral zone, (b) time series of detrended 100 Hz phase and power of the receivers during a period of scintillation, and (c) collocated all-sky images of auroral greenline (557.7 nm) emissions collected at the time intervals marked. The images show that the passage of an auroral arc is associated with the occurrence of amplitude and phase scintillations at 07:16 UT.

Finally, a short (~ 1 km) baseline cluster of GNSS receivers can be used to perform climatological studies related to ionospheric irregularity convection, making it a useful complement to other ground-based sensing modes.

Figure 3.3: (a) A satellite image of the location of the GPS receivers, denoted by the pins. The orange arrows show some baseline distances between receivers. Image modified from the original by Google Earth. (b) GPS phase and power data received from satellite (PRN) 12 at 07:14:45- 07:16:30 UT. (c) Greenline emission (557.7 nm) auroral images taken at Poker Flat Research Range from 07:14:57-07:16:12 UT. The circle represents the local magnetic field line, and the cross represents the line-of-sight from the receiver to the PRN. Credit/Copyright: Gytis Blinstrubas

3.5 Atmosphere-Ionosphere Interactions: Past, Present, and Future Outlook

Much of the discussion and related observing strategies at the end of Chapter 2 also applies here: the important role of IH asymmetries in the overall geospace system response, the need for distributed networks, the need for co-located instrument platforms, the need for interdisciplinary collaborations. However, this Chapter highlights several additional outstanding science questions and the need for additional observations/modeling relevant to AI coupling.

1. A balanced strategy using both ground-based and satellite measurements should be employed to address several outstanding science questions related to the connection between energetic particle precipitation and atmospheric composition (and related climate and atmospheric responses), the dynamics of localized ionospheric plasmas structures/irregularities (e.g., Figure 3.2), and more.
2. Ground-based observations of ozone column densities can be achieved with mm-wave spectroscopy instrumentation and should be employed at a greater number of sites in the Antarctic (and Arctic).
3. Diffuse-like aurora such as pulsating aurora contains the higher energy particle precipitation and so an effort to quantify the occurrence rate and spatial extent in the Antarctic would be extremely valuable to understanding the energy input globally.
4. GNSS receiver arrays can be leveraged within DASHI, not only to provide better spatial coverage for scintillation studies or case-by-case velocity estimation, but also as a distributed instrument itself to more completely investigate irregularity processes.
5. An Incoherent Scatter Radar would open the possibility to study a range of new SWMI and AI coupling processes, as described in the previous solar and space physics decadal survey.

As in the previous Chapter, the topics in this Chapter relate to the wider geospace research community's highest priority research goals and observations for the next decade (NASEM 2024). This includes several overarching science themes and related guiding questions that flow down into the more focused objectives mentioned in this Chapter:

1. Science Theme “Sun-Earth-Space: Our Interconnected Home”

- (a) The overarching question “How do the Sun-Earth system parts interact with each other?” includes focus areas “Magnetic connections across the heliosystem” and “Multiple drivers and feedback mechanisms,” requiring auroral and ionospheric plasma remote sensing measurements and simultaneous observations of auroral and ionospheric processes at both hemispheres (Table 2-1 in NASEM (2024)). The topics described in sections 3.1-3.4 are all related to this overarching question. More broadly, Antarctic geospace observations are essential to address this question as simultaneous measurements in both hemispheres are a requirement.
- (b) The overarching question “How do heliosystem boundaries manifest themselves?” includes focus areas “System impacts of magnetic boundary processes” and “Interactions at plasma-neutral transition regions” and requires multi-plane, multi-altitude measurements of auroral and outflow processes. The topic described in section 3.1, 3.3, and to a lesser extent other sections are related to this overarching question

2. Science Theme “A Laboratory in Space: Building Blocks of Understanding”

- (a) The overarching question “How do fundamental processes create and dissipate explosive phenomena across the heliosphere?” includes focus areas such as the “Response of systems to explosive events,” and requires ground-based observations of high latitude magnetospheric and solar wind energy deposition (Table 2-2 in NASEM (2024)). The topics described in section 3.3 and to a lesser extent other sections relate to this question.
- (b) The overarching question “How do the fundamental processes govern the cross-scale coupling and what are the global properties and consequences of the processes?” includes focus areas such as the “Cross-scale implications of magnetic reconnection” and requires global measurements of key Ionosphere-Thermosphere-Mesosphere (ITM) parameters. The topics described in all sections are relevant to this overarching question.

Finally, although not covered in this report, there are many other science questions related to lidar observations and the ANtarctic Gravity Wave Instrument Net-

work (ANGWIN). These will be discussed in a separate report, though they are closely linked to many of the overarching goals listed above.

4 Space Weather Operations via Antarctic Platforms

“Although ground-based sensors are used across all disciplines of space weather, in terms of long-term support, they have no single clear home in any United States agency or department. This has resulted in an ongoing struggle throughout the community to maintain important space weather sensors and networks.”

Jennifer Gannon et al., *Space Weather*, 2023

Naturally occurring phenomena in space have many significant interactions with as well as major impacts on the Earth and near-Earth space (geospace) environments. This “space weather” is a major national interest of the United States as space weather events can affect technologies “critical to the economy and security of the United States and nations around the world. Technologies such as the electric power grid, the Global Positioning System (GPS), satellite and other space activities, communications, aviation, and pipelines may be degraded or disrupted during space weather events,” (Space Weather Advisory Group 2023). Several example impacts are shown in Figure 4.1.

In this Chapter, we describe the rapidly evolving space weather enterprise and its relation to Antarctic geospace measurements. While space weather is already understood to be a matter of both national and scientific interest, the role of Antarctica in geospace research is often under-emphasized in comparison to mid latitude and northern high latitude regions. In the last 10 years, several pivotal developments have occurred in the United States that motivate a separate Chapter dedicated to discussing these developments and their relation to polar geospace research with a particular focus on Antarctica:

Figure 4.1: Taken from NASEM (2024), Figure 3-7. Space weather impacts are felt in space, on communications through the atmosphere, in the atmosphere, and on ground. Original source: NASA (2021), compiled by the Applied Physics Lab

- The 2015 and 2019 National Space Weather Strategy and Action Plans.
- The passage by the US Congress in 2020 of the Promoting Research and Observations of Space Weather to Improve the Forecasting of Tomorrow (PROSWIFT) Act, which “defines the roles and responsibilities of the Federal departments and agencies, codifies the White House led interagency working group (i.e., the Space Weather Operations, Research, and Mitigation (SWORM) subcommittee), and directs the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), working with SWORM, to establish a Space Weather Advisory Group (SWAG)”
- The publication by SWAG in 2023 of “Findings and Recommendations to Successfully Implement PROSWIFT and Transform the National Space Weather Enterprise” (Space Weather Advisory Group 2023) and in 2024 of the “Results of the First National Survey of User Needs for Space Weather” (Space Weather Advisory Group 2024)
- The release of the solar and space physics decadal survey in 2024 (NASEM 2024), which includes several recommendations related to space weather, including recommendation 3-1 that the “National Science Foundation should develop an agency-wide strategic space weather plan. The plan, as directed by the PROSWIFT Act, should include the incorporation of data streams for space weather purposes from both currently available ground-based facilities and networks, as well as those that would become available after implementation of the decadal survey’s recommendations for ground-based observations. It should also support experimental model development and transition to operations. The development and implementation of the strategic plan is likely to require augmentation to the current level of effort and budget.”

In the last 10+ years geospace research conducted in Antarctica has produced measurements that have validated, constrained, and improved models that are now used for space weather hindcasts (analysis of past events) and operations. In the next 10 years, the need for these measurements will be more important than ever, with an increasing demand for near-real time measurements that can be assimilated into models that produce space weather nowcasts/forecasts for end users such as emergency managers, pilots and airline companies, power grid operators, commercial and defense satellite operators, farmers using precision GNSS equipment, and many others (Space Weather Advisory Group 2024). One goal of this Chapter is to draw direct connections between the current and future needs

of these end users, current and future space weather models and operational data products, and Antarctic geospace measurements.

This report was completed during solar maximum, with several particularly intense geomagnetic storms causing renewed interest in space weather and its impacts on human life and technology. For example, in 2022, during a SpaceX Starlink launch 38 of 49 satellites were lost due to activity related to a geomagnetic storm (Fang et al. 2022, taken from decadal survey). In between the 2023 GEO-SCOPR workshop and the publishing of this report, some of the most intense geomagnetic storms in the last three decades occurred, including the Gannon storm (10-12 May 2024). As satellite launches continue to rise both in number and importance (Figure 4.2), geospace events will in turn become more relevant and potentially devastating. Satellite losses will grow increasingly common, and the impacts and consequences of these losses will affect not only any matters of science, communications, or national security that rely increasingly more on in-situ space measurements, but also economic strain as the overcrowding of low Earth orbit (LEO) with “space junk” makes loss of satellite tracking and collisions more likely. In addition to actions taken to mitigate damage to satellites directly, enhancing and integrating ground-based measurements into space weather prediction models is crucial. This Chapter will discuss the unique and critical role Antarctic geospace measurements play in providing direct, quantifiable improvements to nowcasts and forecasts.

4.1 The role of polar geospace observations in space weather operations: past and present

Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) noted the central importance of high-latitude polar regions to space weather models for several reasons:

- Much of the energy from solar wind/magnetosphere interactions enters the ionosphere/upper atmosphere here making it crucial for modeling global geospace dynamics and potential space weather impacts like atmospheric heating that causes enhanced satellite drag, loss of tracking, and/or unplanned reentry.
- These regions are magnetically connected to geosynchronous orbit where numerous communications satellites are located.

Figure 4.2: Taken from NASEM (2024), Figure 3-1. Caption from NASEM (2024): Growth of space weather services. This figure illustrates the large growth of the NOAA Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC) customer base (blue). This growth is expected to continue as the number of satellites in orbit grows exponentially (pink). While the large space storms associated with solar maximum are associated with extreme space weather, the growth of the customer base continued through the solar minimum around 2020 (as illustrated by the black curve showing the sunspot number). SOURCES: Adapted from NWS/NOAA Space Weather Prediction Center; Satellite data from J. McDowell (2024), <https://planet4589.org>. CC BY 4.0.

- Electrons and ions entering these regions can produce communication disruptions and affect radiation dose for airline passengers and crew.

Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) also noted that “The Antarctic region forms an important source of high latitude data that can be made available in real, or near-real, time for space weather use by government and other agencies. The geography in the Earth’s polar regions makes the Antarctic essentially the only Earth-based platform from which these latitudes can be monitored on a continuous basis and to the highest latitudes.” This fact is no less true today. Major geomagnetic storms in 2023-2025 reinforced the message from IPY4 that “What happens at the poles affects us all” as brilliant aurora usually confined to polar regions were visible and caused space weather impacts across the lower-48 states in the USA.

Measurements from Antarctica are already used to develop and constrain operational space weather data products. For example, Antarctic neutron monitors are part of a global network that delivers crucial measurements of the radiation environment at aviation altitudes used by, for example, the International Civil Aviation Organization. The neutron monitor at South Pole, in particular, is part of the US Simpson Neutron Monitor Network. The Antarctic neutron monitors at Jang Bogo and Mawson are an essential part of the SpaceShip Earth network, providing crucial directional measurements for detecting and analyzing the anisotropies in the cosmic ray and solar energetic particle flux. These monitors are used to understand and mitigate effects of ionizing radiation from galactic cosmic rays and transient solar energetic particle events harmful to the health of airplane crew/passengers as well as avionics. Bain, Onsager, et al. (2023) note “Observational inputs required from the ground-based neutron monitor network must be financially supported for research studies and operations to ensure real-time data is available for forecast operations and actionable end user decision making.” The measurements and related forecasts provide end users information needed to understand impacts to avionics and radiation exposure to crew and passengers, and they are already used by, for example, commercial operators to make decisions such as the diversion of transpolar flights to other routes. Bain, Copeland, et al. (2023) provide several reasons for the need for Antarctic neutron monitors, including the presence of large north-south asymmetries in the radiation environment at aviation altitudes that preclude using solely Arctic or Antarctic observations for research and monitoring. Observations in both hemispheres are needed in order to deliver reliable models and forecasts in either hemisphere. Operational models such as Nowcast of Atmospheric Ionizing Radiation for Aviation Safety (NAIRAS) are increasingly being used by companies to estimate ionizing radiation exposure

on flights, and there is an increasing demand for measurements from both neutron monitors as well as radiation dose measurements on the flights themselves (e.g., Automated Radiation Measurements for Aerospace Safety, ARMAS) to better understand the complex interactions between ionizing radiation, the atmosphere, the aircraft, and the human body.

NOAA's Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC) also provides D Region Absorption Predictions (D-RAP) for different radio frequencies over both the north and south poles. The forecast model used was constrained/validated using riometers exclusively from the Northern Hemisphere. To our knowledge, the model has not yet been validated against Antarctic measurements; thus, given the known asymmetries between the north and south ionosphere, this would be a natural area to target for future improvements to D-RAP. D-RAP has a wide range of potential end users who might rely on HF radio for communications, from the commercial sector to defense/government (e.g., emergency management); this includes USAP (see Section 4.3).

As another example of the use of polar geospace measurements in operational products, NOAA SWPC already uses Total Electron Content (TEC) measurements obtained from networks of North American GNSS receivers to provide their "Global Total Electron Content (GloTEC) model" for "ionosphere situational awareness for users with systems affected by trans-ionospheric radio frequency propagation such as Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and satellite communications." This product is particularly useful for end users interested in impacts related to GNSS positioning and timing accuracy, affecting infrastructure such as autonomous vehicles, drones, etc. Since the Northern Hemisphere is not a mirror image of the South (see Chapter 2), measurements in both hemispheres are needed for space weather data products such as GloTEC: ionospheric dynamics in the south affect the north and vice versa, and measurements in both polar regions are needed as space weather phenomena often develop in polar regions before shifting to and impacting lower latitudes. Figure 4.3 shows an example GloTEC output available on the NOAA SWPC website. End users for this product include farmers who, for example, experienced disruptions and reduced GNSS accuracy for precision farming equipment during the Gannon storm (<https://www.farmprogress.com/technology/did-solar-storm-mess-with-your-planter-s-accuracy->).

The examples above provide some indication of the current and future importance of Antarctic geospace measurements to space weather nowcasts/forecasts, in addition to their longstanding use to validate and constrain space weather models for hindcasts (analysis of past events). However, the growing use of data assimilation techniques in global geospace models suggest they will become much more

Figure 4.3: An example GloTEC model output taken from the NOAA SWPC website.

important in the near future. In particular, since the Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) report ground-based observations from polar regions are more routinely being assimilated in global geospace models. Frameworks such as the Assimilative Modeling of Ionospheric Electrodynamics (AMIE) and Assimilate Mapping of Geospace Observations (AMGeO) ingest data from observations such as SuperDARN and ground-based magnetometers and use them to generate 2D maps of ionospheric parameters; these 2D maps are in turn used as constraints for global geospace models, leading to improvements in event-specific model results (e.g., Figure 4.4). However, as noted in Chapter 2 there are significant gaps in observational coverage in the Southern Hemisphere. For example, Smith et al. (2023) used AMIE to assimilate measurements from 217 magnetometers to constrain a numerical simulation and show major asymmetries in atmospheric heating between the North and South Hemispheres; of the 217 magnetometers, 173 were in the North and 44 in the South. More Southern Hemisphere measurements are needed to model space weather phenomena including atmospheric heating thus better predict space weather impacts such as enhanced satellite drag and unplanned spacecraft re-entry. Northern Hemisphere measurements alone are not sufficient to constrain space weather models given the wide range of space weather phenomena affected by North-South Hemisphere asymmetries.

Finally, ground-based observations in polar regions will be even more important in the coming years as several LEO satellites used to constrain global geospace models are decommissioned. This includes the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program satellites that have previously provided particle and field observations needed to constrain global energy inputs yet will likely be decommissioned in 2025, or continue but without the required particle/field observations in new satellites. Even if these or similar satellites are available, there will be increased demand for dense networks of ground-based observations capable of providing continuous monitoring of both polar regions, supplementing the more sparse and expensive satellite observations and providing key observations that cannot be obtained by satellites (e.g., remote sensing of currents and electric fields at altitudes below the LEO satellites). For example, we already know from modeling and observations that (1) that some of the most intense ionospheric/atmospheric energy deposition events occur in small spatial regions near the cusp, (2) these events can exhibit North-South and East-West Hemisphere asymmetries, and (3) these events can significantly impact global thermospheric heating/expansion and therefore contributed to unwanted effects related to satellite drag such as unplanned/early re-entry and loss of tracking. Distributed ground-based observations such as SuperDARN, GNSS receivers, and ground-based magnetometers are needed to comple-

Figure 4.4: On the top, example forecast geomagnetic disturbance in polar regions from the Space Weather Modeling Framework obtained from NOAA SWPC website. This modeling framework relies on measurements in both hemispheres for hindcast validation and operational model development. At the bottom, example ionospheric Hall conductance output of the AMGeO framework from <https://amgeo.colorado.edu/> which assimilates a range of measurements from both hemispheres (e.g., SuperDARN radar, ground magnetometer) and is already being used to constrain models such as SWMF (e.g., as a boundary condition for ionospheric conductance).

ment sparse satellite measurements in order to capture the temporal and spatial variations associated with such events.

To summarize, in the last ten years polar geospace measurements, including some Antarctic measurements, have been integrated into several operational models. At the same time, they continue to deliver critical measurements needed to validate and constrain space weather models, particularly for phenomena that are sensitive to North-South Hemisphere asymmetries. However, there are several important gaps in monitoring capabilities that should be addressed to improve space weather models and forecasting capabilities. These are reflected in the Space Weather Advisory Group (2024) user needs survey, where several operational needs are discussed that span the electric power, aviation, human space flight, space traffic management and coordination, emergency management, research, and applications of GNSS sectors, all of which relate to national security, the economy, and society. As discussed in the next section, Antarctic geospace measurements can fill many of these gaps and address several user needs.

4.2 The future of space weather operational models using polar geospace observations

This Chapter began with a list of recent developments in the United States related to the national space weather strategy envisioned in PROSWIFT, including SWAG reports (Space Weather Advisory Group 2023; Space Weather Advisory Group 2024) and the decadal survey (NASEM 2024) which list several recommendations related to ground-based monitoring and space weather research in polar regions as well as end user needs (e.g., aviation sector, power grid operators, Department of Defense). In this section, we discuss these recommendations and needs in the context of Antarctic geospace research and monitoring.

SWAG published a report in 2023 with several findings and recommendations related to implementing PROSWIFT (Space Weather Advisory Group 2023). This includes the following Priorities “Provide long-term support for operational ground-based and airborne sensors and networks,” (R.2.1) and “Support coordinated applied research within the thermosphere (above 100 km altitude) which is critical for space traffic coordination,” (R24.1-3) and “Foster and lead a global space weather enterprise” (R25.1-4); all these recommendations are directly relevant to observations from both polar regions. Furthermore, the report notes another broad Priority to “Fund the Federal Space Weather Enterprise”, identifying several extent shortfalls; given the importance of polar regions to a range of space weather

phenomena, support for the types of capital investment needed to, for example, enhance Antarctic observing capabilities should fall under this priority.

As noted by Space Weather Advisory Group (2023), more accurate space weather nowcasts and forecasts require increased ground-based measurement coverage with low latency. However, what density of coverage is needed and where? What sampling rates are required, and what is their latency? Space Weather Advisory Group (2023) notes, “Additionally, consideration should be given to determine the optimal location (e.g., geographical, or orbit) and domain (e.g., ground, air, or space) of these sensors and networks.” Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE) are one method for determining optimal ground-based coverage, as indicated by Recommendation 3-7 in NASEM (2024). Though recently used to examine optimal spacecraft instrumentation and orbits for different applications (e.g., Hsu et al. 2024), they have been seldom used for ground-based space weather measurements. The need for OSSEs is particularly keen in the Antarctic region where logistical resources are constrained with lengthy lead-times needed to deploy new instruments.

There is also a need for multiple stakeholders to participate in these OSSEs and the optimization of ground-based coverage more broadly. For example, rather than having the cryosphere, atmospheric research/meteorology, and space weather communities all deploy GNSS receivers in parallel without consideration of each community’s goals, if all of these communities worked together efficiencies could be identified and used to maximize measurement coverage by, for example, sharing logistical resources via deploying instruments on the same traverse or co-locating instruments using the same platform. This will be discussed further in Chapters 5 and 6.

The recent Solar and Space Physics (Heliophysics) Decadal survey also has several recommendations relevant to Antarctic geospace measurements for space weather monitoring. For example, recommendation 3-1 from NASEM (2024), “The National Science Foundation should develop an agency-wide strategic space weather plan. The plan, as directed by the PROSWIFT Act, should include the incorporation of data streams for space weather purposes from both currently available ground-based facilities and networks, as well as those that would become available after implementation of the decadal survey’s recommendations for ground-based observations. It should also support experimental model development and transition to operations. The development and implementation of the strategic plan is likely to require augmentations to the current level of effort and budget.” Several data streams from Antarctica supported by NSF could be adapted for space weather purposes, including SuperDARN radars, ground magnetometers, GNSS

receivers and other measurements assimilated by frameworks such as AMGeO could be transitioned to operational purposes through, for example, the provision of additional infrastructure (power, satellite internet, etc.) needed for real-time data transfer.

Finally, ground-based observations offer a unique opportunity to monitor key physical quantities in space by leveraging measurements from multiple locations on Earth that magnetically map to corresponding regions in near-Earth space. When coordinated across an array of sensors, these observations can effectively serve as a proxy for measurements from a swarm of satellites, enabling the separation of spatial and temporal variations — an essential capability for accurate space weather monitoring of the magnetosphere. As noted above, such ground-based data may be assimilated into real-time dynamic models. However, the precise mapping between ground observations and the inferred quantities in space remains a significant challenge. Recent advances in machine learning and particularly its ability to uncover complex, non-linear relationships from data offer promising pathways to overcome this limitation. Ground-based measurements of ultra-low frequency (ULF) waves, which govern radial transport of particles in the radiation belts; very-low frequency (VLF) waves, which produce particle acceleration and loss; as well as data from riometers, all-sky cameras, and incoherent scatter radars that provide indirect estimates of particle spectra, will be particularly valuable. Machine learning techniques can help establish robust empirical mappings between these ground-based measurements and space-based physical quantities, ultimately enabling their assimilation into data-driven space weather models.

4.3 The Unique Importance of Space Weather to the US Antarctic Program

People living and working in polar regions experience several direct impacts related to space weather. As such, USAP is an end user for space weather forecasts, for example to ensure backup options during loss of HF radio communications with remote field sites. USAP is also a data provider via, for example, collecting data streams from geospace instrumentation distributed across the continent. NSF OPP/USAP thus are in a unique position to advance the space weather enterprise in the US and internationally. We conclude by listing several space weather impacts of direct relevance to USAP operations and other national polar programs operating in Antarctica and related data collection opportunities:

1. Radiation impacts to avionics and human health on polar flights: USAP uses several aircraft to transport passengers and cargo to Antarctica and across the continent. Collection of radiation dose measurements and anomaly reports by pilots operated by contractors and/or grantees traveling on these aircraft would directly address monitoring data gaps described in Space Weather Advisory Group (2024). Continued neutron monitor measurements with reduced latency, additional riometers for validating operational models, etc. would also improve models such as NAIRAS and lead to better situational awareness for both USAP and the wider aviation community.
2. Ionospheric variability effects on precision navigation solution for a range of logistical support activities: USAP contractors and grantees use precision navigation solutions from GNSS signals for a range of applications, from navigation for traverses/flights to basic research into ice sheet motion. Improved models and monitoring networks are needed for better situational awareness to mitigate impacts related to degraded navigation solutions, improve measurement quality for ice sheet/geodetic studies, etc. GNSS measurements are already available from a wide range of different research communities; as noted in previous sections, OSSEs should be conducted to determine locations where more measurements are needed or where existing measurements should be transitioned to operations and transfer data in near real-time.
3. Radiation impacts on HF radio: USAP uses HF radio for a range of purposes, including backup and emergency communications. Measurements from Antarctic HF receivers at Palmer, McMurdo, and South Pole could be used to inform the use of HF radio for communications during routine operations and emergencies, providing location specific information on continent.
4. Submarine cables for internet connectivity: USAP and other Antarctic programs are considering adding submarine cable links between Antarctica and other continents (RFI Document 2024-27292 [89 FR 92178]), including cables using Science Monitoring And Reliable Telecommunications (SMART) design. These cables present a challenge and an opportunity: a challenge because space weather hazards related to cables are poorly understood in high-latitude regions (e.g., Boteler et al. 2024); an opportunity because hazard assessment models are now available (Chakraborty et al. 2022) and the SMART design enables the collection of critical measurements to quantify hazards and validate related models that can be used by cable operators.

5 Infrastructure and Implementation

“Such rocket observations cannot be made easily at any chosen place. They require ground installation.”

Sydney Chapman, *IGY: Year of Discovery*, 1959

In this Chapter, we briefly summarize the geospace research infrastructure available at the three main US bases in Antarctica (McMurdo, South Pole, Palmer) as well as in the deep field. We also discuss implementation steps to achieve the goals of Chapters 2, 3, and 4. Infrastructure from other countries will be covered in Chapter 6. Much of the information in this section is based on similar material in Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), and we will therefore focus on recent developments. The Chapter frequently refers to commonly used geospace instrumentation; a glossary is provided at the end of the document for readers unfamiliar with these instruments.

5.1 Geospace Research Infrastructure: Past and Present

The three permanent US bases staffed year-round are McMurdo, South Pole, and Palmer (from Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014)):

- **McMurdo Station:** The largest station in Antarctica, American-run McMurdo plays a vital role in the continuation of all ongoing research in the region. In addition to being the gateway to the rest of the continent, McMurdo Station is valuable in its own right as a location to conduct studies. Situated at a magnetic latitude of approximately 80 degrees, the station lies inside the polar cap at all times. Many instruments are housed at Arrival Heights, which provides a quiet area to make measurements.

- **South Pole Station:** Uniquely situated, Amundsen-Scott South Pole Scientific Station features a year-long day-night cycle and an magnetic latitude of 74 degrees. This location means that the station frequently passes through the cusp, and is thus instrumental in the study of cusp-related magnetospheric events. The long, dark winter also results in the station being ideal for light-sensitive observations.
- **Palmer Station:** As the only American Antarctic base north of the Antarctic circle, Palmer station provides a unique vantage point for higher-latitude magnetosphere studies. In addition, it remains the only American base that can be accessed during the Antarctic winter. Palmer Station and Millstone Hill in Massachusetts are approximately magnetically conjugate points, thus providing important interhemispheric observations with complementary instrumentation. The locations are ideal for studies of sub-auroral ionosphere-thermosphere interactions. Millstone Hill has an incoherent scatter radar to provide ionospheric parameters for a better understanding of ionosphere-thermospheric coupling.

See Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014), USAP (2012), and other references for more information about these bases, how they're supplied, etc. Several Antarctic geospace instruments are deployed at these bases, as indicated in the summary in Table 5.1. The instruments in Table 5.1 have been used in many studies and applications described in Chapters 2, 3, and 4 and are all pieces of the "Integrated HelioSystems Laboratory" described in NASEM (2024) that is needed to realize the vision "To discover the secrets of the local cosmos" and "To expand and safeguard humanity's home in space."

Most of the US and international bases are located near the Antarctic coastline, yet as discussed in Chapters 2, 3, and 4, as well as in NASEM (2024) (e.g., page 57), instrumentation at a wide range of latitudes is needed, including far from the coastline. Thus, deep field instrumentation is critical to achieve the scientific goals of observing the geospace environment. Current deep field instrumentation supported by USAP include the Automated Geophysical Observatories (AGO), Autonomous Adaptive Low-Power Instrument Platforms (AAL-PIP), and several GNSS receiver networks.

The AGOs are a collection of remote, unmanned platforms for geophysical monitoring on the Antarctic plateau covering a wide range of latitudes to observe magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling processes in the auroral to polar cap regions. A total of six AGO systems have been deployed. Each AGO site has a fiberglass shelter to house scientific instruments, power control/conditioning units to provide

Instrument	South Pole	McMurdo	Palmer
Neutron Monitor	Y	N	N
Fluxgate Magnetometer	Y	Y	Y
Search Coil Magnetometer	Y	Y	N
Absolute Field Magnetometer	*	N	N
GNSS Receiver	Y	Y	Y
All-Sky Imager	Y	Y	N
Photometers	Y	Y	N
Riometer	Y	Y	N
Low-ELF Receiver	*	Y	Y
ELF/VLF Receiver	Y	Y	Y
LF/MF/HF Receiver	Y	N	N
MF/HF Propagation Receiver	*	*	*
SuperDARN Radar	Y	Y	N

Table 5.1: An overview of the instruments at South Pole, McMurdo and Palmer Stations. Legend: installed but upgrade/service may be needed (Y); new installation needed (*); none installed (N).

Figure 5.1: Coverage of Antarctic magnetometers and GNSS receivers from some of the larger deep field networks mentioned in this report, including POLENET and UKANET GNSS as well as AGO, AALPIP, and BAS LPM. The coverage from these networks increased during and immediately following IPY4 and has been gradually declining since 2017. Based on current trends, there may be no coverage from these networks during IPY5, with all GNSS and magnetometer measurements coming from permanent bases that are mostly located on a few portions of the Antarctic coastline.

100 Watts of power reliably and Iridium telemetry. Generally, each AGO system has a fluxgate and search-coil magnetometers, broad-band riometer, VLF to ELF receivers, scintillation GNSS receiver, and an all-sky imager. Five of the six original AGO observatories also included LF/MF/HF receivers. The AGO power platforms use a totally green renewable energy scheme (i.e., solar and wind) to power a suite of scientific and communication equipment year-round. After several years of experimentation and modification, AGOs have proven their reliable power generation and operation for scientific instrumentation. The project began in the early 1990s. Of the six AGO systems, it appears that only one system (AGO 2) is reporting minimal data (H-component data from the fluxgate magnetometer) via its short-burst data (SBD) protocol as of writing this report. AGO4 is simply sending a message that it is operating but not reporting any science data. The other AGOs (1, 3, 5 and 6) are presumed to be decommissioned. Since the project team (New Jersey Institute of Technology) visited AGO 4 and AGO 5 during the 2019-2020 field season, there has not been further logistics support to service the remote stations. USAP/NSF and the project team made an agreement that the AGO systems will no longer be supported due to the lack of logistics support and thus will be “released to the environment” given the assumption that they are no longer functional.

The AAL-PIPs are designed to operate scientific instruments with low power budgets using solar energy only. Most AAL-PIPs support three instruments: a low-power fluxgate magnetometer, a 3-axis search-coil magnetometer and a GNSS scintillation receiver. The AAL-PIP system is small enough to be transported by the Twin Otter aircraft and installed by two to three people within several days. AAL-PIPs are located in the auroral to polar cap regions along the 40 deg magnetic meridian on the east Antarctic plateau to form a network conjugate to the dense chain of magnetic stations along the west coast of Greenland (operated by Technical University of Denmark). AAL-PIPs are designed for unattended operations for 5 years, utilizing Iridium satellite data links to retrieve data and to send commands to modify the station operation. The deployment of the AAL-PIP network was successfully completed in January 2016, with 6 stations deployed. One system at site PG1, the first in the network to be deployed in 2008, has been returning data for 17 years without any maintenance. Other systems have had maintenance, both remote software patches and during infrequent in-person visits, to maintain operations. At the time of this report, 5 of 6 systems remain operational, including during several recent major geomagnetic storms. The other system, PG2, is currently out of Iridium contact with an unknown issue. All of the systems have operated beyond their expected 5-year lifespan, and it is expected that refurbishment/replacement will soon be needed. Without the AAL-PIPs, and with the decommis-

sioning of the AGO systems as well as the removal of British Antarctic Survey (BAS) Low Power Magnetometers near South Pole in the last few years, there would be no geospace instrumentation in a large area surrounding South Pole Station (apart from at the base itself).

GNSS receiver networks are another major component of deep field infrastructure for monitoring geospace and space weather effects, though the larger networks have typically been operated by other research communities. The networks have grown since the beginning of the twenty-first century thanks to the IPY 2007–2008. Presently, many Antarctic and Arctic GNSS stations form part of a multinational consortium called POLENET (<http://polenet.org/>), which delivers long-term and campaign data. Other important networks include the International GNSS Service (IGS) network (Dow et al. 2009) and UNAVCO network (<https://www.unavco.org/data/gps-gnss/gps-gnss.html>) that are dedicated to geodesy purposes Alfonsi et al. (2022). A map showing much of the current geospace instrument network in Antarctica (run by US and international institutions) is presented Chapter 2 Figure 2.5, with a subset of stations shown in Figure 5.1.

Logistical constraints including weather/ice sheet motion, limited transportation support (airplanes, traverse, etc.), make deploying and maintaining Antarctic instrumentation challenging (USAP 2012), especially in the deep field (NASEM 2021). These constraints have increased in recent years due to budget issues, limited resources (e.g., McMurdo Station renovation) as well as the COVID pandemic related backlog (NASEM 2021) which resulted in reductions in USAP field work opportunities (e.g., NSF 23-117). Much of the current deep field geospace infrastructure deployed by USAP is also aging/past its operational life (e.g., AAL-PIP) or has already been decommissioned (e.g., AGO). If no new geospace instruments are deployed by USAP, US geospace measurements would only be available from McMurdo, South Pole, and Palmer (see Figure 5.1) during the next International Polar Year. Some of these challenges can be addressed via international, interdisciplinary, and commercial partnerships as will be discussed in Chapter 6. They can also be addressed through advances in reliable, autonomous measurement systems for harsh, remote environments (to reduce the need for maintenance trips) and new capabilities such as light traverses using trucks (next section).

5.2 Future Observing Strategies and Implementation

In this section, we discuss observing strategies needed to address the goals of Chapter 2, 3, and 4. We also discuss potential realistic implementation options

taking into account discussions at the GEOSCOPR workshop and findings of recent reports (e.g., NASEM 2021) related to current logistical support capabilities.

5.2.1 Observing Strategies

First, we reiterate from earlier Chapters that there are several critical science questions and space weather monitoring needs from NASEM 2024, Space Weather Advisory Group 2023, other consensus studies, and the discussion at the GEOSCOPR workshop that can only be addressed with Antarctic geospace measurements. The need for investments in ground-based Antarctic infrastructure is also addressed in NASEM (2024). This includes recommendations 3-1 and 5-2 for the development of the “Distributed Arrays of Small Heterogeneous Instruments” (DASHI) Mid-Scale Research Infrastructure-1 concept to support both fundamental research and space weather operations, leveraging existing instrumentation while also intelligently (i.e., with support of Observation System Simulation Experiments) planning future deployments. It also includes the support of other high-priority geospace research instruments that may not directly fall under DASHI or have only partial overlap (Table 5-2 in NASEM (2024)). Addressing these questions will require a blend of partnerships (e.g., international) and increased efficiencies with existing USAP support through, for example, leveraged interdisciplinary partnerships. Many of the recommendations in past reports and consensus studies remain relevant and could facilitate these activities. We summarize these below.

5.2.2 Implementation

Implementing the observing strategies listed in the previous subsection will require USAP support as well as the capabilities of other partners (e.g., traverses conducted by other countries); the latter will be discussed in more depth in Chapter 6. In this subsection, we discuss implementation while remaining mostly agnostic on whether USAP or another partner is involved. We focus on two primary areas of implementation: (1) infrastructure at bases and (2) infrastructure in the deep field.

First, we revisit implementation steps suggested roughly 12 years ago when the Antarctic geospace research community last compiled a similar workshop report. Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) described several observing strategies that include a blend of measurements at permanent bases and in the deep field, including instrument networks such as the “Interior Antarctic Array,” the “Scalable West Antarctic Array,” and the “Polar International Collaboration for Atmospheric

Dynamics and Aeronomy" (PICADA) including the Antarctic Gravity Wave Imaging Network (ANGWIN). Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) also notes the need for infrastructure upgrades at several bases, including:

- McMurdo: An enhanced Arrival Heights Observatory to satisfy several major science objectives, as well as movement of an Incoherent Scatter Radar to McMurdo.
- South Pole: Development of a modest remote sub-station 5-8 km from the station for conducting certain types of geophysical research that are affected by RF and optical interference (similar to past facilities used for the South Pole Remote Earth Science and Seismological Observatory, or SPRESSO).

Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax (2014) describe the scientific rationale for these steps (see their Chapter 6). We note that (1) much of the scientific rationale remains the same, particularly in cases where the steps have not yet been implemented, (2) some of the steps have been implemented (e.g., ANGWIN, elements of the Interior Antarctic Array) while others have not (South Pole sub-station, Scalable West Antarctic Array, moving incoherent scatter radar), and (3) in some cases steps were implemented by international partners or were partly implemented through serendipitous/unplanned interdisciplinary partnerships (e.g., POLENET provides some observations in West and East Antarctica).

Since much of the GEOSOPR workshop was dedicated to discussing scientific priorities (see Chapters 2, 3, 4) and not specific implementation steps, we shall focus the remainder of this section on the implementation of one particular goal relevant to the Decadal Survey (NASEM 2024). To be sure, there are other high-priority observing strategies and related implementation steps, but we leave discussion of these for future reports since this is not a consensus study. We also refer the reader to discussion in the Decadal Survey (NASEM 2024), which highlights the importance of many of the instruments discussed above (e.g., SuperDARN, GNSS receivers, magnetometers, lidars) in addressing high-priority science questions over the next 10 years as part of the "Integrated HelioSystems Laboratory" as well as contributing to the implementation of the PROSWIFT Act (i.e., space weather operations). In particular, recommendation 5-1 of NASEM 2024 notes "NSF should conduct regular portfolio reviews and consider the current and potential roles of ground-based instruments relevant to the HSL during these reviews. Renewal or recompetition of continuing operations of existing instruments should include consideration of their contributions to the HSL." Recommendation 3-1 of NASEM 2024 notes that a new NSF strategic space weather plan, as directed

by PROSWIFT, should “include the incorporation of data streams for space weather purposes from both currently available ground-based facilities and networks, as well as those that would become available...”

Antarctic measurements would be expected to be a key component of DASHI (recommendation 5-2 of NASEM 2024, see above). The first step in implementing DASHI requires an investigation of optimal observation locations; NASEM 2024 recommends this be accomplished via the Mid-Scale Research Infrastructure-1 program which would enable the intelligent design of the network (e.g., via Observing System Simulation Experiments), though it could also be accomplished via smaller targeted grants for polar regions, mid-latitudes, equatorial regions, etc. At the GEOSCOPR workshop, attendees discussed opportunities to co-fund these development activities across different NSF programs, as they are relevant to multiple programs. Since the workshop, many NSF programs were reorganized, though it would still be advantageous to explore co-funding DASHI planning grants via several programs across the Directorate of Geosciences including the AGS - Geospace Cluster and Polar Programs - Antarctic Research.

The second step in implementing DASHI involves deployment of new instrument platforms and/or refurbishment of existing platforms. Although it is out of scope for this report to discuss specific deployment locations as these would be determined as part of the DASHI development stage, it's highly likely (given discussion at the GEOSCOPR workshop, in Lessard, Gerrard, and Weatherwax 2014, and in NASEM 2024) that some automated instrument platforms would be deployed in the deep field while others would be deployed at bases operated by the US and international partners. Strategies for accomplishing deep field deployments in line with DASHI were discussed at the GEOSCOPR workshop and subsequent meetings, as well as recent reports NASEM (2021), and the need for light traverse routes was repeatedly stressed.

For example, NASEM (2021) notes several challenges in deep field deployments related to reduced availability of fixed wing resources, and light traverse routes (e.g., with trucks) could alleviate some of these challenges. Shared research traverse routes useful to multiple research areas were recommended in NASEM (2021) to reach deep field-locations. At the time of this report, light traverses with trucks have already been successfully used by the seismology community to support a distributed network near South Pole. Future science traverses could support multiple disciplines simultaneously, reducing logistical burdens and increasing efficiency. NASEM (2021) note that “One opportunity highlighted by the scientific community is to have logistics based (i.e., location-based) research calls for deep-field locations. To identify geographic regions currently of broad scientific interest,

OPP could issue a call for letters of intent/interest.” This specific recommendation would be particularly helpful in implementing the DASHI concept; though there are overarching regions of interest for DASHI, there is some flexibility in setting the specific geographic locations for instrumentation. Finally, international partnerships and other partnerships would also support the development and implementation of the DASHI concept, as discussed in Chapter 6.

6 Partnerships: International, National, Interdisciplinary, and Industry

“In this era of instant communications and global connectivity, it might seem surprising that the global scientific community is so excited by a scientific strategy that was developed more than 100 years ago. Because it was indeed back in 1882-1883 that the idea of holding a focused, internationally-coordinated year of polar research – an International Polar Year – was first developed. At that point in history, the poles were blank white spaces on maps and the cutting edge communications technology was the telegraph. The decision to coordinate with other nations rather than compete, and to focus on research to understand polar phenomena rather than acquisition of territory, was something new and exciting. That first IPY in 1882-83 and subsequent ones in 1932-33 and the International Geophysical Year (IGY) in 1957-58, drew great minds and generated great leaders; these “international years” set a precedent of cooperation in science that, while innovative at the time, is considered the norm today.”

Robin Bell, U.S. Senate testimony, 2006

In this Chapter, we summarize international, national, interdisciplinary, and commercial partnerships that can enable the science investigations and related implementation described in Chapters 2-5.

6.1 International Partnerships

6.1.1 SCAR, Representing the US in the Scientific Committee for Antarctic Research

The Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) is an international organization that was created during the 1957-1958 International Geophysical Year (IGY) with the intent to continue the international scientific cooperation that was a hallmark of the IGY. SCAR's work addresses all aspects of Antarctic and Southern Ocean science and how research results can be used to inform policy related to the environmental management of this unique region.

For 65 years SCAR has successfully addressed and accomplished its two-fold mission of:

1. Facilitating international scientific research collaboration in the Antarctic and Southern Ocean, and on the role of the Antarctic region in the Earth system
2. Providing objective and independent scientific advice to the Antarctic Treaty System and other international policy bodies.

The US is a founding member of SCAR and American scientists have played a major and significant role in all aspects of SCAR's work. The Polar Research Board (PRB) of the National Academies is the US National Committee to SCAR and responsible for appointing delegates and representatives to SCAR. The US-SCAR team represents the US Antarctic scientific community and is a focal point for US participation in SCAR. US-SCAR is funded by a grant from NSF which has a primary goal to encourage more US scientists to become involved with SCAR. In addition to the PRB appointees, over 250 US scientists are formally affiliated with SCAR groups, and many others participate in various SCAR activities.

Currently, US-SCAR is working to keep the US Antarctic community aware of continuing and new initiatives relating to research about and from Antarctica through a variety of efforts, including organizing bi-annual virtual US Antarctic Science Meetings, maintaining an email list, broadcasting on social media, providing financial travel support for US scientists (especially early career researchers) to attend international SCAR meetings, compiling a formal Directory of US Antarctic Scientists, and expanding an interview series about US Antarctic researchers.

Figure 6.1: Map of SCAR Member Countries (<https://scar.org/about-us/governance/members>): 34 Full Members (dark blue) and 12 Associate Members (light blue), with delegates listed at <https://scar.org/about-us/leadership/delegates>. There are also 9 International Science Council unions as SCAR Members.

6.1.2 National Science Foundation Support for International Collaborations

NSF supports international collaborations in several ways. This includes formal cost-sharing agreements where a proposal to fund investigators in both countries is submitted to a lead agency and reviewed by a single panel. One example of this type of agreement is the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between NSF and the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) in the UK, which enables joint proposals involving field work with one or both of USAP and the British Antarctic Survey. As noted by NASEM (2021), these special proposals are highly desirable as they avoid the “‘double jeopardy’ pathway of separate proposal submission to each national funding agency.”

NSF also supports informal agreements between US investigators and international partners, and these types of international collaborations are supported via, for example, proposals submitted to NSF with an MOU between a PI/university in the US and investigators in other countries. Proposals are often encouraged that relate to unique opportunities or capabilities that a foreign partner provides (e.g., a new scientific traverse, a new instrument network) that complement capabilities in the US. They have typically also been encouraged when a major international effort is underway. This includes the fourth international polar year (National Research Council 2012b) and would be expected to also include the upcoming fifth international polar year in 2032-2033. It also includes other major efforts with international organizations such as SCAR, including Scientific Research Programmes (SRP) conceived to be overarching programmes focused on high priority topical areas, see next section.

There are many recent examples of successful collaborations in both categories (see box below). These collaborations have been critical in maintaining geospace research capabilities in parts of Antarctica that are challenging for USAP to access.

Examples of Recent International Collaborations Supported by NSF

- **United States-United Kingdom:** A few recent examples of US partners working with the British Antarctic Survey (BAS) include (1) a grant to support for search-coil magnetometers provided by the University of New Hampshire that are operated at Rothera and Halley stations, (2) a separate grant to support for the operation of autonomous magnetometer systems in a 2D network that includes the BAS Low-Power Magnetometers (LPM) and AAL-PIPs (supported by both NSF AGS and OPP, enabled the data product shown in Figure 2.4).
- **United States-Germany-Korea-Canada:** Multiple groups from GFZ Potsdam, AWI, Kyung Hee University, University of Colorado, and New Jersey Institute of technology are involved in deploying instrumentation at Neumayer Station. Kyung Hee University provided a search-coil magnetometer built in house based on the University of New Hampshire design. The development was made possible through technology transfer. Additionally, two all-sky imagers were installed by GFZ Potsdam and the University of Calgary in collaboration with Hyomin Kim/NJIT who provided a riometer. Finally, a ULF induction coil magnetometer (up to 500 Hz) and a VLF receiver (300 Hz to 30 kHz) were recently installed at Neumayer station through a collaboration between the University of Colorado (Robert Marshall) and GFZ/AWI.
- **United States-Korea:** Multiple groups from Korea Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Kyung Hee University, and New Jersey Institute of Technology. Kyung Hee University provided a search-coil magnetometer built in house based on the University of New Hampshire design. Next-generation AGO systems will be tested at Jang Bogo Station and be deployed in the deep polar cap regions. The logistics will be provided by KOPRI. The new AGO systems are funded by the NSF OPP (PI: Hyomin Kim).
- **United States-Canada:** The group at Dartmouth College is working with University of New Brunswick to enable observations of LF/MF/HF natural auroral radio emissions at magnetically conjugate locations at South Pole Station and at one of the observatories of the Canadian high-arctic ionospheric network (CHAIN) on Baffin Island.

In addition to the above examples, the Polar Observing Network (POLENET)

ANET (US Antarctic Network) and international partner projects (UK Antarctic Network [UKANET], CAPGIA, VLNDEF,...) is an excellent example of a large international collaboration that has been leveraged by the geospace research community for ionospheric research. In particular, this large network of GNSS receivers and other instruments has provided a substantial increase in ionospheric monitoring capabilities in regions of Antarctica with no other geospace research instrumentation.

Recently, a new Scientific Research Programme, Antarctic Geospace and ATmosphere reseArch (AGATA), has been approved by SCAR. AGATA is a coordinated, worldwide effort to monitor, investigate and better understand the physics of the polar atmosphere and the impact of the Sun-Earth interactions on the polar regions. AGATA will take advantage of existing and planned instrumentation in Antarctica, but also in the Arctic and satellite-based observations, and it will aim for coordinated research efforts and data exchange. This bi-polar perspective will allow the study of significant interhemispheric asymmetries in the atmospheric response observed in the polar regions. Significant efforts will be spent to promote international collaboration. AGATA is now setting up its international governance representing the many different scientific communities ensuring geographical and gender mix, and representation of early career researchers. Among the actions that will facilitate the international coordination AGATA can endorse activities and funding proposals of third parties if they align with the goals of AGATA SRP. AGATA runs through at least 2032 with a possibility for further extension, thus will provide a major pathway for facilitating international partnerships crucial for supporting the fifth International Polar Year (IPY5, 2032-2033).

Another important aspect of AGATA is the capacity building and training program for early career researchers, which can also be seen in the context of preparation for IPY5. It is hoped that this report, as well as the recent AGATA SRP and related resources (Alfonsi et al. 2022), can be used to inform this process. IPY's are opportunities for compelling science objectives that can only be addressed through ambitious international and interdisciplinary projects that span both poles and address compelling science objectives. POLENET is an excellent example of the type of effort that IPY5 and efforts such as AGATA can enable. Maintaining and expanding POLENET with additional geospace instruments (e.g., magnetometer) at key locations would satisfy many of the outstanding research questions in Chapters 2 and 3 as well as pave the way for improved space weather forecasts described in Chapter 4.

6.2 National Partnerships (Other Agencies)

There are many examples of existing partnerships across agencies in the United States. For example, the NASA Scientific Balloon program frequently launches from McMurdo Station with support from USAP, and the US Geological Survey operates several magnetometers in Antarctica (co-located with seismometers) in partnership with USAP. As another example, NASA grant solicitations in the HelioPhysics Division can support research involving Antarctic measurements, while NSF grant solicitations (e.g., Antarctic Research) can support research involving the use of NASA satellite measurements. As a final example, the PROSWIFT Act (Chapter 4) codified the White House led interagency working group that defines roles within and across agencies to implement the national space weather enterprise, involving specific roles within NSF, NASA, Department of Interior, Department of Defense, etc. At the GEOSOPR workshop, NSF and NASA partnerships came up perhaps the most frequently, though others were discussed as well. One example involved the crucial importance of Antarctic geospace measurements to fill gaps that may arise in satellite-monitoring of space weather phenomena, including gaps that were projected to arise in geospace monitoring from the loss of Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) particle and field measurements.

More broadly, NASEM 2024 calls for “An enhanced coordinated, multiagency space weather research and operations program” as part of an integrated “HelioSystems Laboratory” that is “managed and operated in a coordinated fashion to obtain the joint observations required to address the science of the next decade.” Recommendation 5-1 of NASEM 2024 has several more specific recommendations relevant to NSF, including:

1. NASA, NSF, and NOAA should create an HSL working group to develop tools and standards for the scientific community to coordinate joint observations of NASA, NSF, NOAA, and international assets. The goal is to encourage joint observing campaigns by making collaboration easier.
2. Early in the pre-formulation phase of each new space mission, NSF, NASA, and NOAA, possibly in collaboration with international partners, should hold strategic discussions about potential contributed ground-based components that could enhance the science return.
3. NSF should conduct regular portfolio reviews and consider the current and potential roles of ground-based instruments relevant to the HSL during these

reviews. Renewal or recompetition of continuing operations of existing instruments should include consideration of their contributions to the HSL.

In the context of this report, implementing this recommendation could mean involvement of Antarctic geospace researchers (e.g., modelers using Antarctic data, instrument teams) in future NASA mission Science and Technology Definition Teams. It could also mean coordination between NSF and NASA in the form of, for example, targeted grant solicitations for polar ground-based measurements and/or related analysis that enables transformative science investigations when combined with upcoming NASA satellite missions. It could also mean the consideration of the value of Antarctic ground-based measurements to the broader HSL during reviews.

Recommendation 5-10 of NASEM 2024 also states that NASA and NSF “should expand and coordinate opportunities for carrying out scientific research that combines ground- and space-based observations. Grant funding opportunities should continue to enable and enhance joint analysis of ground-space data as appropriate. NSF and NASA should offer additional funding opportunities that support joint aggregation, assimilation, and analysis of ground- and space-based data and production and archiving of combined ground-space data products.”

6.3 Interdisciplinary Partnerships

Interdisciplinary collaboration may include communities that already operate instrumentation of interest to the geospace research community, communities targeting similar interdisciplinary science questions (Chapters 2 and 3), and/or communities that operate in regions of interest to the geospace research community and can co-deploy instruments. Examples of such collaborations include GNSS receiver networks co-deployed with the cryosphere community, seismology instrument platforms that include seismometers and magnetometers, terrestrial and space weather monitoring packages, and shared light traverse routes (see Chapter 5 for the latter). For a more comprehensive list of possible interdisciplinary partnerships, see the recent review by Scheinert et al. 2026.

Recommendation 5-12 of NASEM 2024 states that NASA and NSF “should actively contribute to a cultural change that would better foster cross-divisional research. Specifically, they should increase support for crossdivisional research by (1) Gearing research and data analysis programs toward better supporting cross-disciplinary projects. Mechanisms could include stating interdisciplinary goals in

proposal calls, explicitly identifying calls that may span multiple divisions or directorates and improving the review process—for example, by broadening the panelist expertise, (2) Initiating and funding interdisciplinary workshops to advance and develop crossdisciplinary collaborations...” In the context of the GEOSCOPR workshop and Antarctic geospace research more broadly, this could involve targeted research calls in support of interdisciplinary research during the next International Polar year and/or support for International Polar Year planning workshops. NSF has already supported an IPY-focused workshop organized by NASEM in May 2025, and similar future workshops targeted to specific IPY-related objectives (e.g., planning interdisciplinary instrument networks) could be one way to address this recommendation.

Recommendation 5-13 of NASEM 2024 states that NSF “should address the challenges that arise from having the subdisciplines of solar physics, heliospheric physics, geospace sciences, space weather, and plasma physics managed within different directorates and divisions. NSF should conduct a study to examine possible organizational structures within the foundation that would serve these disciplines in an optimal way.” At the time of this report, NSF has recently undergone a significant reorganization, including the formation of the Geospace Cluster, that addresses many of the issues outlined by this recommendation.

6.4 Industry Partnerships

Although not significantly discussed at the GEOSCOPR workshop, we briefly note that partnerships with industry may also prove beneficial in implementing many of the recommendations of this report. As one example, the Canadian High Arctic Ionospheric Network (CHAIN) has been successful in partnering with commercial aviation companies that support the collection of geospace measurements for targeted space weather products. Similar partnerships may also work in the Antarctic, since space weather monitoring in this region is needed to understand a range of space weather impacts globally (see Chapter 4).

7 State of the Profession, Education, and Outreach

“Furthermore, the IGY was also a poor man’s programme. Irrespective of the scientific level of the country or of the institutions, there was scope for useful contribution from all. Some of the observations could be undertaken with relatively simple instruments, such as: the reception of signals from broadcast transmitters or atmospherics in the LF and VLF, experiments on atmospheric electricity, meteorological observations with groundbased sensors or with radiosondes that were being undertaken in any case as part of the country’s weather service, photography of auroras with simple cameras on the ground, the simple telescopic arrangement introduced, after Sputnik I was launched, to obtain approximate positions of an orbiting satellite in the programme called ‘Moonwatch’.”

A.P. Mitra, 1957

In this section, we draw from discussions at the GEOSCOPR workshop as well as the recent solar and space physics decadal survey (NASSEM 2024) to describe several topics related to the current state of the profession, education, and outreach related to Antarctic geospace research. Though recent challenges have made it difficult to recruit and train the next generation of researchers, Antarctic research continues to excite and inspire the general public and scientists alike. This Chapter discusses challenges and opportunities that are unique to Antarctic geospace research as well as ones that are common across all geospace research areas. This includes a discussion of several opportunities to maintain a healthy workforce of geospace researchers via existing and possible future NSF programs.

7.1 Sustaining Research in Critical Areas

Polar regions are important for understanding a range of processes driving global changes, including space weather and the Earth's magnetosphere. Sustaining research in these critical areas requires a continuous influx of skilled scientists to address the emerging challenges of geospace science. Building a robust pipeline of future researchers ensures the advancement of scientific knowledge and the maintenance of current research efforts. Polar geospace studies demand long-term commitments due to the nature of instrument deployment and data collection, which spans decades. Supporting these initiatives requires funding agencies to prioritize workforce recruitment and retention development, educational outreach, and public engagement.

Expanding opportunities for student research is a crucial step in sustaining this research, including increased support for summer schools, workshops, and other skill-building activities tailored to undergraduate and graduate students. Providing stipends and equal, fair access to resources will ensure broader participation. Additionally, public outreach programs such as STEAM initiatives and citizen science projects can inspire the next generation of geospace researchers by highlighting the societal relevance of solar and space physics.

Another vital aspect of sustaining research is articulating the value of solar and space physics as a career path. It's important that future NASA, NOAA, and NSF programs account for not only inspiring, interesting, and personally fulfilling work but also factors such as work-life balance, career stability, and financial compensation. Polar research presents unique challenges, including months-long field deployments in remote, harsh environments; separation from family; and limited resources within tight timeframes during the Antarctic summer. Addressing these challenges requires enhanced support systems such as flexible career pathways, resources for maintaining physical and mental well-being, and recognition of the personal sacrifices made by researchers in polar regions.

Another critical challenge in Antarctic research is addressing sexual assault and harassment. The 2022 NSF OPP USAP 'Sexual Assault/Harassment Prevention and Response' report (SAHPR 2022) highlights the heightened risks in isolated field-work settings, such as those in Antarctica. The report states: 'The isolated work settings of the USAP, combined with living in close quarters far from home, create a dynamic that blurs personal and professional boundaries. This makes it harder to establish clear boundaries, intervene as bystanders, hold peers accountable, and report unwanted behaviors' (p. 13–14). Implementing the report's recommendations will help create a safer and more welcoming environment for all researchers,

including those in geospace science.

7.2 Addressing Expertise Gaps and Ensuring Continuity of Long-Term Research Programs

The specialized nature of geospace science, especially in polar regions, highlights the critical need for addressing expertise gaps. As current experts retire or transition to other roles, there is an urgent need to cultivate a new generation of scientists equipped to lead long-term research efforts. Developing a workforce with interdisciplinary expertise in areas such as data science, artificial intelligence, and computational modeling is essential for addressing the evolving needs of the field. This applies to both the fundamental research that has traditionally been conducted in Antarctica, as well as more applied space weather operations that utilizes Antarctic measurements (see Chapter 4). For example, Recommendation 13.6 from Space Weather Advisory Group (2023) is to “Promote career pathways for interdisciplinary technologists supporting the space weather enterprise,” including data scientists, instrument scientists, software engineers, and others.

Long-term research programs in polar geospace science rely on consistent data collection and analysis over decades. Ensuring continuity requires strategic investment in educational initiatives, such as NSF’s Faculty Development in Geospace Science (FDSS) program (see Recommendation 4-3 of recent decadal survey (NASEM 2024)) and other bridge programs like SOARS. These initiatives provide critical mentoring and research opportunities to students from communities who haven’t had access to similar programs before, enabling their transition into leadership roles. Increased funding levels from agencies like NASA, NOAA, and NSF for individual investigator grants would also provide stability for early-career researchers and reduce career fragmentation caused by reliance on multiple short-term grants.

7.3 Encouraging Innovation and New Perspectives

A well-trained pipeline of scientists from different communities and backgrounds fosters innovation by bringing fresh ideas and novel approaches to longstanding research challenges. Including individuals from varied backgrounds enhances creativity and drives breakthroughs in technology and understanding. To achieve this, the geospace research community must prioritize outreach efforts that introduce solar and space physics to K-12 and early college students. The absence of these

topics in standard astronomy and physics textbooks limits exposure, reducing the recruitment of students into the field. This is consistent with the recent decadal survey's Recommendation 4-2 (NASEM 2024), "Funding agencies should expand the reach of solar and space sciences in education by expanding the definition of the National Science Foundation's 'broader impacts/societal impacts' and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration's 'broadening impacts' to specifically include developing solar and space science educational materials aimed at K-12 and college students."

Programs like NSF REUs, NASA's Heliophysics Summer School, and FINESST fellowships play a pivotal role in providing authentic research experiences that retain students in STEM. Additionally, STEAM initiatives—integrating art into STEM—can enhance public engagement by making complex scientific concepts more understandable through visual and creative mediums. Collaborative projects with artists and writers can transform public communication materials, inspiring a broader audience to engage with geospace science.

NASA's Heliophysics Big Year (Reiff et al. 2026) inspired numerous opportunities for education and citizen science campaigns. These spanned a range of audiences and scopes, from concerted nationwide programs and distributed data collection affiliated with satellite missions (Mesquita et al. 2025) to low-cost educational activities (Ozturk 2025). Section 6 of Usis et al. 2026 notes the heritage of the IPY system in the Heliophysics Big Year and provides a discussion of design criteria for citizen science campaigns, particularly in geospace. Scientists and educators can build upon the infrastructure developed and lessons learned from the Heliophysics Big Year and past NSF-supported citizen science projects (e.g., observing campaigns related to the 2021 Antarctic total solar eclipse, Figure 7.1) to strengthen geospace education, public outreach and citizen science in IPY5.

7.4 Enhancing Collaboration and Global Engagement

Geospace science is inherently collaborative, often requiring international partnerships to address complex, large-scale challenges. Building a global pipeline of scientists strengthens these collaborations and broadens the scope of research. Initiatives like the proposed heliophysics consortium can create centralized career resource centers, advertise different career pathways, and enhance workforce development by fostering global partnerships.

International collaborations are particularly vital in polar geospace research, where logistical challenges necessitate shared resources and expertise. Contin-

Figure 7.1: Artwork to commemorate the 2021 Antarctic Eclipse Festival, a HamSCI citizen science campaign organized around the December 2021 Antarctic eclipse. IPY5 will span two high latitude eclipses, on 9 May 2032 and 30 March 2033, presenting opportunities for similar campaigns. CC BY-ND.

ued support from NSF and other agencies for polar measurement projects that span multiple countries and programs are fundamental for coordinating efforts to achieve shared scientific goals. A well-developed workforce enhances these collaborations by incorporating different perspectives and skills, ensuring the continued success of geospace research in polar regions.

Overall, the geospace research profession must prioritize sustaining a healthy, vibrant workforce that includes many different communities and backgrounds. This involves addressing expertise gaps, fostering innovation, and enhancing global engagement through targeted educational, outreach, and funding initiatives. By doing so, the field can ensure its readiness to meet future challenges and continue its critical contributions to understanding the Earth's polar regions and beyond.

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Glossary

All-Sky Cameras (ASI) Low-light cameras that use a fish-eye lens to collect light from the entire sky. They are used for a wide range of science investigations, including observations of aurora (luminosity due to electron or proton precipitation into the upper atmosphere) and airglow (luminosity associated with thermospheric winds). As such, their capabilities vary significantly from one implementation to the next, including the passbands of their optical filters, integration times and sample rates, etc..

bow shock The shockwave formed due to the interaction of the solar wind with the Earth's magnetosphere, which serves to deflect many solar wind particles around Earth.

citizen science Research undertaken by the general public, typically in collaboration with research specialists.

Digital ionosondes (or digisondes) Transmits HF signals in the frequency band of 3-30 Mhz vertically upward, sweeping through a range of HF frequencies designed to probe the lower E-region of the ionosphere up to the F-region maximum peak density. Each "pulse" reflects from the ionosphere at an altitude where the plasma frequency equals the transmission frequency. The transmission time of the signal is then used to estimate the altitudes at which the particular plasma frequency is observed, from which ionospheric densities can be calculated, In addition to these basic measurements, Doppler shifts are often measured to provide information about the line of sight velocity of the layer..

dipole A field characterized by the presence of two connected points, or poles.

ELF/VLF/MF/HF Receivers The designations refer to “Extremely Low”, “Very Low,” “Medium,” and “High” Frequency receivers, encompassing a range of frequencies from near 100 Hz up to several MHz. Naturally occurring signals are common throughout this entire range and include those with magnetospheric and ionosphere Origins. These receivers also measure subionospheric propagation of artificial signals, including transmitters of opportunity such as AM radio stations from Southern Hemisphere countries and timing signals from various national observatories, as well as occasional dedicated science transmissions. These studies enable investigation of ionospheric propagation..

Fabry-Perot Interferometer (FPI) An FPI is a passive optical device that utilizes a Fabry-Perot etalon to measure airglow and/or auroral spectral emission. These spectra are analyzed so as to infer Doppler widths (constituent temperatures) and Doppler shifts (constituent winds) from some reference source. Common FPIs use OI 630-nm airglow emission from the thermosphere and 557-nm airglow emission from the mesopause, though both lines are also auroral lines which can lead to ambiguity during active conditions. FPI devices are most commonly associated with dark observing conditions, as the sunlight overwhelms weaker airglow and auroral emissions..

Fluxgate Magnetometer Fluxgate magnetometers are designed to provide a measure of magnetic fields that are static or slowly changing. A fluxgate magnetometer’s main components include a highly permeable core, an excitation coil used to drive the ferromagnetic core in and out of saturation, and a sense/feedback coil that is used to measure the resulting field, which is a combination of the driven and background fields. The strength and direction of the background field either reinforces or inhibits the ease of saturation in one direction versus the other and is presented as variations in the sensed output waveform..

geomagnetic conjugates Two or more locations in the Earth’s magnetosphere that are connected by the same field line.

geospace The region encompassing the earth’s atmosphere, ionosphere, thermosphere, and magnetosphere.

GNSS/TEC Receivers Receivers for Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), such as the commonly used Global Positioning System (GPS), that are utilized in

upper atmospheric work are typically capable of scintillation monitoring. These GNSS receivers collect high-rate (50-Hz) phase and amplitude data on all visible satellites, along with low rate data which includes the standard deviation of phase ($\sigma\phi$), amplitude variation (S4), and total electron content (TEC). GNSS observations are typically used to study small scale ionospheric irregularities..

Incoherent and Coherent Scatter Radar (ISR and CSR) Large active radar arrays, ISRs are used to study the plasma conditions of the ionosphere. By pulsing signals at frequencies from several hundred MHz to 1,200 MHz, these devices can infer the line-of-sight velocity of ions, ion and electron temperatures and electron density, as well as infer (under certain conditions) neutral particle temperature and flow. These antennas are necessarily large, ranging in size from 32 meter diameter dishes to 300 m x 300m dipole arrays. One type of ISR is the Advanced Modular Incoherent Scatter Radar (AMISR) technology, which allows variable sensitivity and modular setup. Because these arrays feature no moving parts, they do not require personnel on hand to operate. Sensitivity of the facility may be altered by adding or subtracting dipoles to the array. Operating on the same principles as ISRs, CSRs utilize beams that are in-phase with each other. This allows more precise Doppler resolution, and increases the signal-to-noise ratio of the data..

Induction Coil Magnetometer Also known as search-coil magnetometers, these are designed specifically to measure fluctuations in magnetic fields with periods the order of fractions of a second. Induction coil magnetometers consist of a mu-metal core surrounded by tens of thousands of turns of wire, which respond to a changing magnetic field by inducing a current that may be read and recorded. Their advantage over fluxgate magnetometers is their increased sensitivity at frequencies ranging from a few tens of mHz up to several Hz..

interhemispheric In geospace research, refers to the comparison between two hemispheres of a celestial body, *e.g.*, Earth's Northern and Southern hemispheres.

interhemispheric asymmetry A difference between two hemispheres at geomagnetically conjugate points.

ionosphere One of the layers of the Earth's atmosphere, characterized by a prevalence of ionized particles.

Lidar Light Detection And Ranging techniques are very similar to radar techniques, but utilize laser emissions tuned to a specific wavelength to profile atmospheric, aerosol, and species backscatter. Most lidar systems cover the troposphere to the lower thermosphere, and can measure neutral atmospheric temperatures and aerosol backscatter coefficients. Depending on the wavelength used, some lidars can also measure constituent density, thus leading to the colloquialism of “Na lidar” or “Fe lidar”. Some lidar systems can also measure neutral winds, depending on the level of technology (i.e., cost) of the transmitter and receiver systems..

magnetopause The boundary between the Earth’s confined magnetosphere and the solar wind.

magnetosheath The region in the magnetosphere between the magnetopause and the bow shock.

magnetosphere The portion of the magnetic field produced by a celestial body and impacted by other interplanetary magnetic fields and plasmas.

Neutron Monitor These instruments detect secondary neutrons that are produced by cosmic rays interacting with the Earth’s atmosphere. They are used for many applications, including space weather operational data products used by the aviation sector (see Chapter 4).

Photomultiplier Tube (PMT) Photomultiplier Tubes are also used to make aurora and airglow observations, but are simpler and much less expensive than allsky cameras. Typically used with fixed-width collimators and sometimes used with scanning mirrors, their sensitivities range from near-infrared to ultraviolet wavelengths. These instruments utilize a vacuum tube with kilovolt-scale potentials to excite and multiply photoelectrons induced from the observed wavelengths. PMTs thus measure a current proportional to the intensity of the incident light..

plasma A collection of particles similar to a gas that are characterized by having charge and both creating and being subject to electromagnetic fields.

PSWS Personal Space Weather Station.

Riometer Short for “Relative Ionosphere Opacitymeter”, this instrument provides a measure of ionospheric conductivity and can show signatures of precipitation of electrons having energies often tens of keV. The instrument accomplishes this by monitoring the power levels of naturally occurring signals in a portion of the 30 MHz radio band continuously. When ionospheric conductivity is increased as a result of the precipitation, the wave power passing through the ionosphere is attenuated. The variations in signal strength thus provide an indirect measure of precipitation, even in a sunlit ionosphere. Imaging riometers use arrays of riometers and generate 2-dimensional images of enhanced conductivity derived from the relative phases of measured signals.

solar wind The stream of plasma emitted by the sun which interacts with the Earth’s magnetosphere.

space weather The physical and phenomenological state of the natural space environment, including the Sun and the interplanetary and planetary environments..

Super Dual Auroral Radar Network (SuperDARN) A network of 35+ radars, SuperDARN maintains a presence in both hemispheres, composed of ~25 northern and ~11 southern radars (number of operational/funded radars varies year to year). Operating between 8 and 20 MHz, this system studies Doppler characteristics of the ionosphere along 16 azimuth lines, providing a 50 degree field of view..